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Social Network Analysis of Food System Science Networks

Deliverable 2.1

Trang Nguyen, Bobby Tsvetkov, Kelly Rijswijk, Vittoria Ruggiero, Sofia Mendes, Thom Achterbosch

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Executive summary

Introduction

There has been rapid growth in the volume of academic papers and research projects that address interconnections in the food system. This study examines the collaborative relations and structures within food systems science in Europe after an era of expansion, fuelled by research policy and funding. The scope of the analysis is the community established by and through the collaborative research project European Food Systems Science Network, in short FoSSNet.

Methods

The methods applied are 1) survey-based social network analysis centred on relations among individual researchers and practitioners and linkages to hubs for food systems science, and 2) participatory validation through workshops in 12 European countries. The insights obtained are used to derive challenges and opportunities for developing a network as part of a science-policy-society interface for food system transformation.

Results

The sample of the SNA comprised 186 predominantly mid- to late-career scientists (61% women), characterised by multidisciplinary and international reach across 85 organisations in 16 countries. Through collaborations largely centred on research activities, the network of connections expanded to 870 individuals representing 385 organisations across 35 countries. Structurally, it formed a large but sparse network with a moderately connected core and many peripheral actors, where a small number of highly connected brokers played a crucial role in maintaining cross-organisational and cross-national connectivity.

The FoSSNet community functioned as a “network of networks”, with survey respondents collectively engaged in at least 114 food systems projects and over 197 networks, primarily at European and national scales, indicating extensive cross-platform involvement. Portfolio mapping of the 22 most cited initiatives showed strong coverage of governance, policy, innovation, and nutrition-related themes, but comparatively weaker engagement in other domains, such as environmental conditions, suggesting network-level gaps in representation.

Country-level social network analysis (restricted to countries with ≥ 10 responses and $\geq 80\%$ response rates) showed substantial variation in community structures: most national workshops’ groups of participants displayed a central core built around longer-term collaborations, while the German sample showed no central component, with respondents, who were mostly not social scientists, indicating individual, non-overlapping connections, suggesting reach towards less common collaborations. Across countries, collaboration was predominantly research-oriented and scientist-led, with limited policy and private-sector representation. The Netherlands and Denmark showed stronger international integration. Some variation existed in non-research collaboration modes (e.g. communication, private-sector dialogue, or education).

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Six interrelated structural gaps in the network were identified, including (1) weak bridging across communities (2) hub dependency (3) limited collaboration beyond research (4) restricted engagement outside academia (5) barriers for early-career researchers, and (6) uneven geographical coverage. In general, workshop discussions highlighted that these gaps are systemic and mutually reinforcing, suggesting that strengthening interdisciplinarity, transdisciplinarity, and inclusivity could act as leverage points for improving network resilience, diversity, and policy relevance.

Despite broad agreement on several issues, distinct perspectives emerged among participants from different countries. For example, while there was general agreement that linkages between industry and academia are weak, Latvia presented an outlier case, highlighting a strong existing synergy between the two that appears less prevalent in some Western European contexts. Although hub dependence was suggested to be a vulnerability, Dutch participants offered a counter-narrative, suggesting that specialisation can foster resilience if “orchestrators” of the network effectively bridge gaps through inclusive agenda-setting, while also recognising potential power asymmetries, as noted by Portuguese participants. There was also recognised variation across scales: whereas hub dependence is more evident at the European level, where power and visibility are concentrated in a relatively small number of institutions and countries, local-level networks appear more horizontally distributed, with a broader range of actors and a more balanced distribution of influence, according to the Spanish perspective.

Recommendations

The feedback workshops also identified a series of recommendations to strengthen the contribution of the emerging food systems science network to the science-policy-society interface for food systems transformation. For integration and resilience, FoSSNet should invest in shared language, transparent governance, and incentives for boundary-spanning roles that connect disciplines, sectors, and regions. This includes facilitating interdisciplinary collaboration (e.g. senior–junior partnerships and stronger inclusion of Central and Eastern European members), creating structured spaces for engagement with policy, industry, and civil society, and embedding cocreation models that balance power and protect less powerful actors. Education, mentorship, and mobility schemes can enhance food systems literacy, support early-career researchers, and promote more balanced participation across countries. Long-term and more equitably distributed funding, alongside advocacy to reduce hub dependency, is essential for sustaining trust and collaboration beyond short-term projects. Overall, FoSSNet should consolidate its role as an active broker, using dedicated intermediaries, targeted communication, and structured dialogue to strengthen its impact within the science–policy–society interface.

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Authors	Trang Nguyen (WUR), Bobby Tsvetkov (WUR), Kelly Rijswijk (WUR), Vittoria Ruggiero (EUFIC), Sofia Mendes (EUFIC), Thom Achterbosch (WUR)
Contributors	EIT Food, RUC, INRAE, BLE, DIL, U Pisa, BSC, IRWIR PAN, UCP, UB, U Lund, VU, UOXF

Reviewers	Technical review	Saher Hasnain (Roskilde University - RUC)
	Technical review	Staņislavs Œeiko (Baltic Studies Centre -BSC)

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
ECR	Early Career Researcher
EU	Europe/European
FSS	Food System Science
NGO	Non-governmental Organisation
SNA	Social Network Analysis
SPSI	Science-policy-society interface

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1 Introduction

Food system research, which addresses food as a system of interconnected relations, is a fast-growing field. In response to global challenges related to food insecurity and the impact of agriculture and food on planetary and human health, actors in academia, business, civil society and policy increasingly explore systemic linkages. For example, researchers study how agricultural production, supply chains, retail environments and household practices jointly shape food insecurity and diet-related health outcomes, and how changes in one part of the system ripple through others, for instance, by developing nutrition-sensitive value chains, urban food policies and climate-smart farming initiatives.

Due to its systemic perspective it has been argued that food system research is an integrative and integrating field of science with strong relations between science and society - a field that weaves together academic disciplines and traditions; formal and traditional knowledges; knowledge from fields of practice such as farming and fishery, food processing, food service, waste management, education, innovation, finance and policy (Mcbean, 2021; Singh et al., 2023; Ingram et al., 2025). The evolving food system science has thus led to the building of relations, schools, communities and networks, for example the Feast2030 network and the Food2030 network, exploring differing approaches and perspectives.

This report contributes to the literature on food systems by examining the current state of social relations within the field of food system research, specifically in Europe. It focuses on two research actions that support the development of a pan-European network for food systems science. First, we report on a survey-based social network analysis (SNA) (Task 2.1). Second, we report on the validation of the SNA through a series of national workshops held across Europe (Task 2.2).

1.1 Motivation

The need for a better structure for knowledge on food systems

Food systems science (FSS) is an expanding research domain. Research mappings at global and European level illustrated a rapid expansion of academic papers and research project that address interconnections in the food system. An inventory identified that 434 research articles and reports that address the food system were published in 2019-2024, in English language alone (Lopez et al., 2025). For comparison, the same paper tallied over 100 publications on agricultural systems and more than 600 on energy systems in the SCOPUS database for the same period.

Inventories performed in 2019 and 2023 of EU-funded R&I projects that apply a food systems approach identified 30 and 50 projects, respectively (Achterbosch et al., 2019;

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Scaramuzzi et al., 2023). At present, nearly 90 European projects on food system research are active in the Food 2030 Networks, a project community established under the project CLEVERFOOD. The projects covered under this network have a total budget of more than 550 million euro and comprise more than 90 living labs for innovation in the food system. This alone represents 6% of the entire food-related cluster (cluster 6) (9bn euro for 2021-2027)¹.

In addition, the FutureFoodS partnership, another funding pipeline under Horizon Europe, has recently granted funds for a batch of 23 research projects on food systems research, and is expected to mobilise in total 250 million euro of grant funding for projects within the next 5 years. Scholars have identified the potential of FutureFoodS and the Food 2030 networks for supporting the development of transformative and mission-driven food systems R&I (Kok et al. 2025).

Despite the expansion of FSS research, the knowledge and innovation (K&I) system governing Europe's food system was deemed insufficient in representation and process to address the emerging challenges of nourishing Europe in a healthy, sustainable and fair way (Tsvetkov et al. 2024; Papargyropoulou et al. 2025). There is growing awareness that while satisfying food demand has been largely met, the desired health and environmental outcomes require greater input and interaction with society and other stakeholders, and this calls for a new approach to K&I (see, e.g. Gasparatos et al., 2023; Pascucci, 2025). Several research projects on the governance of food system research have addressed this question for the EU, for example FIT4FOOD2030, FOSTER, CLEVERFOOD, FOODPaths), resulting in identified practices for transdisciplinary research in EU to address the large-scale complex challenges of food system transformation. Collaborative approaches at European level have been applied in projects with various orientations, including innovation, food policy action, policy analysis and digitalisation.

In this regard, the required transformation needs to be underpinned by an enhanced governance system drawing together food system science with other academic disciplines and other knowledge brokers (that of practitioners in policy and system transformation), in order to design a new K&I system which follows the principles of transparency, fairness, equality and effectiveness (Singh et al. 2023). It is relevant to explore what contribution to improved governance would stem from establishing a food systems science network. to harness existing knowledge and create new ways to collaborate and integrate food systems thinking.

The project Pan-European Food Systems Science Network – short name FoSSNet – aims to strengthen academic networks and support cross-disciplinary knowledge exchange, building the foundation for a strong K&I governance structure for Europe's food system. While such food system transformation also requires political change, behavior change and other structural adjustments, in FoSSNet the focus lies on the knowledge dimension. To overcome the limitations of the current K&I system, the project promotes (i) making the inter-and transdisciplinary FSS activities more responsive to current and future demands; and (ii) addressing the associated

¹ [Horizon Europe – creating knowledge and innovation for sustainable agriculture, forestry and rural communities | EU CAP Network](#)

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governance structure that is required to advance this type of integrative FSS for food system transformation.

Propelling food system science within a science-policy-society interface

Inter- and transdisciplinarity lies at the core of the food system research, and this has important implications for network building (Den Boer et al. 2021a). Scaramuzzi et al. (2023) derive commonalities from a set of 30 best practices on the implementation of the food system approach: all projects address multiple food system components and their interconnections; all projects adopt an interdisciplinary approach; almost all projects employ a multi-stakeholder approach. Further principles have been identified in terms of the incorporation of feedback loops and interconnections (Halberg and Westhoek, 2019) and the inclusion of diverse perspectives and knowledges, such as traditional and practitioner's knowledge (Pruse et al., forthcoming).

Applying transformative food system research and innovation (R&I) requires moving beyond linear, siloed approaches towards systemic and transdisciplinary modes of working across sectors and governance levels (den Boer et al., 2021a; Sonnino, 2023). This shift entails the development of specific competencies, including food systems thinking, collaborative skills, and the capacity for knowledge cocreation. Although inter- and transdisciplinary educational initiatives are emerging in Europe, current R&I systems remain largely fragmented, with monodisciplinary structures and sectoral incentives still dominant (den Boer et al., 2021b). Addressing this gap between systemic ambition and practical implementation calls for stronger emphasis on competence development among researchers, policymakers and other food system actors, alongside governance approaches that foster more integrated and collaborative food systems science (den Boer et al., 2021a; Sonnino, 2023).

Without effective collaboration, efforts to undertake inter- and transdisciplinary research on food systems are likely to face significant limitations. From past and ongoing collaborative efforts, relations emerge between scientists and practitioners in industry, civil society and policy. Substantial shortcomings have been identified in the science-policy-society interface for food systems transformation (Singh et al. 2023). The aim of FoSSNet is to harness the relations within that community into a Europe-wide network for food system science. As a starting point for establishing such a network, it is important to understand the current state of the interactions and relationships between actors and what connects them.

1.2 Objectives

A social network analysis (SNA) supports the development of this understanding by systematically mapping and analysing network relations. It provides insight how patterns of relationships influence information exchange, innovation and collective action. In this study SNA is applied to the scientists and scientific institutions active in the field of food systems science. **The objective of the study is to generate an evidence-**

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based insight into the structural patterns in the network related to food systems science across Europe.

The scope of the analysis is the community established by and through the collaborative research project FoSSNet. By empirically documenting patterns of interaction and collaboration in the FoSSNet community, the study aims to understand relations in the science field in the EU. There are strong limitations that stem from the bias in the sample, and which limit the opportunities for applying generalised conclusions on the networks of FSS in Europe. The main strategies in the study design to overcome sample bias and enhance the external validity of the study are, first, to apply the survey instrument in two rounds, initially on European level followed by a validation at national levels, and to collect qualitative data through workshops that validate the outcomes of the initial survey. (Chapter 2 provides further detail.)

By disclosing the structural patterns of the FoSSNet community, as pars pro toto for the European community on food system science, the study aims to provide insights for several specific purposes:

First, the SNA identifies the gaps and limitations in the network. The study will inform the understanding of these gaps as basis for shaping activities for the mobilisation and engagement of a diverse set of academic networks operating at European, national, and regional levels. By identifying existing linkages and degrees of connectivity, the analysis provides a foundation for strengthening engagement strategies and for broadening participation in the FoSSNet community.

Second, the SNA seeks to contribute to the conceptual clarification of FoSSNet itself by helping to define the functional boundaries of the network. Through mapping who is connected, how, and around which activities, the analysis supports a clearer understanding of what constitutes the FoSSNet network, both in terms of its core actors, its wider ecosystem of affiliated stakeholders, and the range of activities that the network can engage in to exercise its functions.

Third, beyond descriptive mapping, the SNA is designed as a strategic tool to enhance network functioning. The analysis examines how stakeholders are interconnected, which actors or organisations occupy central or bridging positions, and which forms of collaboration, such as research, education, or policy engagement, are most prominent. This enables the identification of key hubs, collaboration clusters, and structural dependencies within the network.

Fourth, the SNA supports characterising the level of inclusiveness and balance of the network by analysing representation across geographic regions, scientific disciplines, and institutional types. This informs the project how well different parts of Europe and different strands of FSS are integrated within the FoSSNet community, and to identify areas of over- or under-representation.

Finally, the analysis explicitly aims to identify opportunities for improvement in network performance, and for growing from a science community into a science network. By detecting gaps in collaboration, knowledge exchange, and information flows, as well as

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blind spots in disciplinary or geographic coverage, the SNA provides a basis for discussion on understanding these limitations and generating actionable insights to strengthen the FSS network. The feedback workshops, implemented in twelve European countries, directly built on that basis, went beyond describing the structural patterns by shedding light on the factors that shape them and identifying practical concrete recommendations to enhance the network's functioning.

These various objectives jointly lead to the following Research Question:

What are the collaborative relations and structures within food system science in Europe, and what are gaps and opportunities for developing a network as part of a science-policy-society interface for food system transformation?

Chapter 2 describes the research design and empirical strategy. This is followed by the results from the SNA survey (chapter 3) and the feedback workshops (chapter 4). The final chapter provides a synthesis and a future-oriented perspective on the social network for food system science in Europe.

2 Methodology

2.1 Research design

Social network analysis (SNA) is a versatile tool for examining the systemic organisation of actors and the structure of their connectedness using network theory (Borgatti et al., 2009; Scott, 2013; Knoke & Yang, 2021). It has been widely applied to study collaboration patterns within research and innovation communities. For example, Bianco Bozzo & Tomassini (2024) used secondary data of researchers' curriculum vitae to analyse collaboration networks in agricultural research in Uruguay. Hermans et al. (2017) applied SNA to multi-stakeholder platforms in agricultural research across three countries to identify opportunities and constraints for innovation and scaling. Vishnu et al. (2020) combined household-level interviews with participant farmers and key project stakeholders, supplemented by participatory rural appraisal techniques, to examine structural challenges in smallholder dairy production systems.

For this study, we followed a mixed quantitative-qualitative approach which was also adopted by D'Amato et al. (2025) who studied the landscape of actors at the biodiversity science-policy-society interface in Europe, although with important methodological differences. Their study followed an organisation-based design: representatives of organisations were interviewed, and the sampling frame was constructed through a literature review rather than through a survey-based network mapping. The qualitative component focused on the roles of different actors in knowledge cocreation and their potential contributions to the functioning of a Science Service for Biodiversity.

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In contrast, our mixed-methods approach followed a sequential logic (see Figure 1). First, SNA was used to assess the structural characteristics of the FoSSNet community and to identify gaps in connectedness and participation. Second, feedback workshops provided qualitative insights that helped explain the observed structural patterns and inform recommendations for strengthening the network. By combining structural diagnosis with participant reflection, this approach strengthens both the validity and the practical relevance of the findings. It not only explains what the network looks like. It also helps clarify why it takes that form and how it might be improved, thereby directly informing actionable recommendations for strengthening the network.

Data collection for the SNA survey took place in late 2024. The first results were presented during an interactive session at the first European food system science conference in Oxford in the Spring of 2025. This session, which presented the key gaps in the network identified by the SNA, served both to gather initial comments on the results and to pilot the format for the feedback workshops planned in the FoSSNet partner countries.

The workshops were organised by FoSSNet partners between July and November 2025, making use of their national networks and schedules. During the workshops, in an interval of 15-20 minutes, participants completed the standardised SNA survey. The national feedback workshops yielded contextual information and explanations of the gaps identified before and suggested gap-closing recommendations.

Figure 1. Research components contributing to the deliverable's objectives

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2.2 Analytical framework

Based on a preliminary version of the conceptual framework for FoSSNet (Ingram et al., 2025), we developed an analytical framework for the social network analysis (SNA), which then informed the design of the SNA survey. The analytical framework translated the deliverable's objectives into a set of guiding research questions that structure the subsequent analysis:

- Who is part of the network, and what is the level of inclusion within the network?
- How is the FSS community organised and how are relationships distributed across the network?
- What are the network's key current functions, as inferred from observed collaboration patterns?
- What are the gaps and opportunities in the network, as revealed by its structure, and how do these hamper or improve the network's functioning?

Addressing these research questions required conceptual clarity regarding what constitutes food systems science, who is recognised as a part of a food systems science network, and how relationships and functions within such a network are defined and interpreted. Network boundaries are not self-evident; they are constructed through definitional choices that shape who is included, who remains peripheral, and how influence and participation are understood. Without making these underlying assumptions explicit, analytical results risk obscuring important inclusion and exclusion dynamics or overlooking divergent actor perspectives. The conceptual framework, therefore, served to clarify key terms, analytical units, and boundary assumptions that underpin the SNA. By articulating these terms, the framework created transparency around how the network is delineated and enabled a more critical examination of representation, structural positioning and potential areas of contestation within the evolving food systems science landscape.

Clarifying definitions

To bridge FoSSNet's objectives with our research questions and the SNA, we defined its boundaries regarding the definition of terms such as food system science, social network, and a food system science network.

Our working definition² of food system science is as follows:

² The definition was developed and agreed upon by the FoSSNet team members, but has not been shared with a broader group of stakeholders to reach a consensus. It is an adaptation from the working definition that was presented at the first project conference and informed the analytical framework: *"Food system science weaves together knowledges on the dynamic relationships including feedbacks between food system drivers, core activities, [supporting services] and outcomes, to study and foster transformative action on innovation, conservation, restoration and exnovation in interconnected social, economic and biophysical systems."* In the validation workshops the adapted version was presented for discussion.

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Food System Science is the interdisciplinary study of food system drivers, core activities, outcomes and feedbacks, and their dynamic, two-way relationships across time and space. FSS requires a systems approach to integrate diverse knowledges in an independent, transparent, democratic, participatory, fair and equitable way, recognising social, cultural, political, economic and biophysical contexts. FSS is needed to better understand and foster transformative action in policy and practice on innovation, conservation, restoration and exnovation in interconnected social, economic and biophysical systems. Such action helps transition towards more sustainable, resilient, and nature- and people-positive food systems. Source: own elaboration by the FoSSNet consortium based on Ingram et al. (2025)

This definition of food systems science highlights both the analytical breadth of the field and its explicitly transformative orientation. Importantly, it also implies heterogeneity among food system scientists in terms of how comprehensively they engage with different food system components and feedback loops.

FSS typically involves multidisciplinary, interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary research. In this report we applied the following the definition of these terms:

“multidisciplinary research gathers diverse expert perspectives on a single issue; interdisciplinary research integrates theories and methodologies into a unified approach for complex problems; and transdisciplinary research collaboratively develops solutions to real-world societal challenges, transcending the boundaries of a single academic discipline and academic and non-academic worlds”. (FoSSNet deliverable D3.2, Concept for a toolkit for transdisciplinary research)

To capture this diversity within the network, the conceptual framework distinguished between different levels of food system science engagement, reflecting variation in disciplinary orientation, systems integration, and attention to feedback dynamics. This distinction provided a conceptual basis for later assessing epistemic diversity and inclusion within the FoSSNet network.

Food system science considers four aspects of a food system: drivers, activities, outcomes and feedback loops (Ingram et al., 2025). The scope and depth to which knowledge actors apply the lens of FSS in research can be categorised accordingly. Level 1 are (mostly disciplinary) science users looking at 1 aspect of a food system. Level 2 are (more inter or transdisciplinary oriented) science users that look at two aspects of a food system, and they may or may not include the feedback loop between these parts. Level 3 are food system science users that look at all 4 aspects of a food system, including the feedback loops between the drivers, activities and outcomes. All these science users work in various domains that belong to interconnected social, economic and biophysical systems.

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Figure 2. Types of users

While food defined the around which organised, the development social and relationships science is and mobilised. understanding science as a field analysis of

food system science

system science substantive domain FoSSNet is network focused on the institutional through which this produced, shared, To move from an of food systems of inquiry to an FoSSNet as a

collective endeavour, it was therefore necessary to conceptualise the connections among food systems scientists as a social network. This shift enabled the examination of actors and relationships as empirical objects of analysis, rather than treating collaboration as an implicit or assumed feature of the field.

To derive the definition of a food system science network, we first followed the classic definition of a social network (Yang et al, 2017, p.5):

“A social network consists of a set of nodes (sometimes referred to as actors or vertices in graph theory) connected via some type of relations, which are also called ties, links, arcs, or edges”.

From this generic definition, we derived the following definition of a FSS network:

“A food systems science network consists of a set of nodes (stakeholders representing the interests of one or more sectors in science, government, citizens, private business) connected via collaborative research, funding partnerships, or policy advisory roles that facilitate the exchange of knowledge, resources and information across the field of food system science.”

The first leg of the definition clarifies the actors in the FSS networks as stakeholders across sectors that are connected via different relationships governed by the field of FSS. The second leg suggests the types of connections these stakeholders may have in the exchange of knowledge, resources and information across the field of food system science.

Functions of a food system science network

The European Commission aims to develop a European Research Area (ERA) for food systems. Recommendation 2021/2122 of the European Council established the "Pact for Research and Innovation in Europe," which served as the cornerstone for

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relaunching the European Research Area (ERA). The ERA targets five areas: research careers and research infrastructures, gender equality and open science, knowledge valorisation, citizen engagement, and stronger institutions. The European Commission aims to develop a European Research Area (ERA) for food systems that enhances a European-wide food system knowledge base, and fosters cross-sectoral innovation and policy dialogue on eleven transition challenges for the EU food system (Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (European Commission) et al., 2023). Under this approach, the European Commission aims to establish a governance structure that provides the necessary conditions for actors in research and innovation (R&I) to address the challenges related to the food system in a collaborative and mission-orientated approach. This includes centralized data platforms, such as the EU food system monitoring framework hosted by the Joint Research Centre, or the envisaged observatory under the Partnership for a Sustainable Future of Food Systems (FutureFoodS). Knowledge brokers within the field collate and disseminate food systems research and translate it into adequate and effective policies. Through what functions would a network for food system science contribute to this ambition on the ERA for food systems?

Knowledge cocreation

We adopted the description by D'Amato et al. (2025) of processes of cocreation of knowledge. Following the literature on relations of science to society, emphasis was placed on the notion that processes of research and discovery are not fundamentally different within academia as between researchers and societal actors:

'Knowledge cocreation entails the framing, collating, and dissemination of knowledge "through social interaction and change" (Forsyth, 2003, p. 104) and typically involves different actors (e.g., researchers and research organizations, experts and practitioners, interest groups, government organizations and their agencies, civil society organizations and citizen groups) (Tinch et al., 2018). In other words, "the many ways in which scientists, policy makers and others link up to communicate, exchange ideas, and jointly develop knowledge for enriching policy and decision-making processes and/or research" (Young et al., 2013). They are collaborative and nonlinear processes that open spaces "for debate over conflicting beliefs, values and interests" (Kelemen et al., 2021, p. 92). As such, they may be more or less formalized in terms of institutional arrangements and governance systems (e.g., well-established and recurring platforms vs. small, one-off interactions) and functions and aims (e.g., explicit vs. tacit). ...Outputs are also varied, taking the form of, among others, written reports, workshops, and dialogues (Miller & Wyborn, 2020). As dynamic entities, they influence and are influenced by the wider environment where they operate, and they can change over time, for example, in terms of intents or actor composition and relations.' (D'Amato et al., 2025, p. 2)

Knowledge cocreation encompasses the entire temporal and conceptual process of multidisciplinary research, as defined above. The functionalities of a food system science network would be to provide a platform for researchers and food system actors to communicate, exchange ideas, and jointly develop knowledge for engaging in

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research and innovation. A network would also provide a platform for debate over conflicting beliefs, values and interests, and enriching policy and decision-making processes. The activities for knowledge cocreation in a network would include workshops, dialogues, and joint writing.

Collaboration on education and food system literacy

There is concern that Europe's future workforce may not be adequately equipped to address the large-scale systemic problems related to ongoing climate crisis and global food insecurity (Urias & Rao, 2024). Food systems education is therefore a leverage point in the transition toward more sustainable, resilient, and nature- and people-positive food systems. In the literature on education related to food system challenges, the emphasis in education processes shifted from knowledge to skills to be developed; learning shifted from formal training to continuous learning (Jönsson et al., 2025).

A comprehensive overview of food systems education in higher education institutions in Europe identified several shortcomings (Urias & Rao, 2024): Many universities treat food system challenges as separate, disconnected issues, hindering effective transformation. Uncertainty persists about whether students—especially those in nutrition and dietetics—are equipped with the necessary knowledge and skills. University efforts often limit to minor practices like waste management, which yield minimal impact without broader institutional policies. Other scholars have identified the shortcomings in primary and secondary education and in professional education and continuous learning. In the academic literature, food systems literacy has evolved as an overarching framework for defining the learning needs, knowledge and skills across the cognitive levels and across the stages of citizenship and professional life (Pope et al., 2021; Silveira, 2025).

Jönsson et al. (2025) identify opportunities in collaboration higher education - focus primarily on Master's programs (ISCED level 7), as they were the most prevalent and offered a standardized framework for comparison. Initiated in 1999, the Bologna Process has helped harmonize higher education across Europe by establishing common structures and learning outcome frameworks for Master's programs, and recent comparative studies (e.g., Burleigh and Jönsson 2024) provide a basis for this approach. While a few Bachelor's and continuing education programs were also included, the findings primarily reflect Master's-level education.

The function of a food systems science network in the domain of education and learning would be to foster interdisciplinary collaboration and collaboration in the interface of science with education and society. First, a network approach would support the assessment of the strengths and gaps of current educational offerings and evaluation which disciplines need greater involvement. Second, it would further seek to clarify the crucial skills and expertise required for future professionals, assess the impact of emerging technologies, and provide an opportunity for participants to contribute suggestions for advancing the field. Third, it would support the knowledge cocreation in the design of educational programs with learning outcomes/objectives on

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food systems dimensions (i.e., society, environment, health, policy, etc.), the development of soft skills (i.e., critical thinking, creativity, leadership, resilience, etc.), mobility components (students and/or staff learning at multiple sites) and involvement of practitioners from the realms of industry and other private sector, civil society and policy.

Collaboration in the science-policy-society interface (SPSI)

Science-policy-society interfaces (SPSIs) are defined as a set of processes, structures, and relationships that link science, policymaking, and society to enable cocreation and use of knowledge for food system transformation. SPSIs are dynamic and adaptive networks that create continuous, multi-directional exchanges among researchers, decision-makers, and societal groups, supporting functions such as monitoring, assessment, capacity building, and coordination across scales (Singh et al., 2023). The description by D'Amato et al. (2025) of actors operating in the SPSI for biodiversity science is transferable to food system science:

“Organizations participating in the science–policy–society interface may squarely fall into one type (e.g., science actor, policy actor, practitioner) or may be boundary organizations (i.e., organizations operating across multiple domains) (Pitt et al., 2018). Nonetheless, all organizations still maintain their own institutional positions, values, agendas, objectives, capacities, and needs (e.g., knowledge provision, data management, knowledge requesting, knowledge brokering, funding, capacity building, advocacy or lobbying) (Balian et al., 2012; Wang & Ahmed, 2005). Notably, within organizations, individuals may or may not fully align with organizational posture.” (D'Amato et al., 2025, p. 3)

A food systems science network would be tailored towards the needs of knowledge provision, data management, knowledge requesting, knowledge brokering, funding, capacity building, advocacy or lobbying.

To our knowledge, there is no complete inventory of the network configurations for knowledge cocreation in food systems science in Europe. The European Commission's register for expert groups lists over two dozen expert groups related to agriculture and food, formal and informal. Those expert groups which comprise of stakeholder representations or experts frequently have direct relations to research and innovation networks (Achterbosch & Bogaardt, 2022). Knowledge hubs, technology platforms and innovation centres aim to synthesise research outcomes and inform research and innovation policy. A report on food policy networks in urban settings mentions the following configurations within the European geography: assembly; city deal; consortium; food policy council; food policy network; industry interest group; alternative food or agriculture or urban network; informal solidarity economy or community-supported agriculture network; partnership (Edwards et al., 2023). Food policy networks are defined as “endorsed by relevant institutions from the quadruple helix – can constitute a broad and inclusive science-policy-practice interface that generates transformative knowledge, supports the formulation and implementation of

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integrated urban food policies and empowers food system actors around a shared vision of the urban food system (Edwards et al., 2023). Communities of practice bring together stakeholders from research and practice. For example, the EAT Forum, a civil society group, established communities of action for addressing food system challenges, which included sector-oriented communities for chefs and food service, cities, healthcare professionals, finance & trade, and science (<https://eatforum.org/initiative/eat-communities-for-action/>). In living labs, field labs and innovation hubs, stakeholders collaborate with research and innovation actors to experiment with solutions in a real-life setting, or test-bed.

Applying a network-of-network approach has been suggested by an expert group of the European Commission as a pathway to develop SPSI for food system transformations (Singh et al., 2023; Webb et al., 2022). The science-policy-society interface faces several persistent problems, including insecure and fragmented funding, limited and unstable human resources, and misaligned timeframes and expectations between researchers and decision makers. It is also hindered by weak networking structures and insufficient communication capacities across disciplines, sectors, and societal groups. To respond to these challenges, a “network-of-networks” model has been proposed as a promising way to strengthen and better coordinate these interfaces. This refers to the capacity of organizations to interact in and transform wider networks of actors by mobilizing existing relations, capabilities, and resources to boost the effectiveness and meaningfulness of science-policy-society interface processes (Kelemen et al., 2021). A well-structured network of networks enhances efficiency by fostering effective communication, collaboration, and resource sharing, which reduces redundancy and promotes inclusivity (SanClements et al., 2022). In this context, the role of the food systems science network would be to mobilize and enhance the efforts of existing organizations, platforms, networks, and activities working at the food system science-policy-society interface to improve knowledge accessibility, reduce redundancies, fill gaps, and improve outreach to knowledge users.

Because the governance of food system issues in the EU is characterized by multifaceted contentious issues, which also pervade the structures for research and innovation (Duncan et al., 2022; van Zanten et al., 2025), a key challenge of a food systems science network would be to ensure inclusiveness and manage vested interests while supporting evidence-informed learning and decision-making processes. This would demand acknowledging, managing, and coordinating the diverse actors, capabilities, and interests outlined above. Criteria to evaluate the success of science-policy-society interfaces relate to their ability to produce credible (i.e., valid, reliable), relevant (i.e., timely, useful), and legitimate (i.e., value plural) outcomes (Heink et al., 2015).

Functions of a food systems science network and possible activities of its members

Building on these insights, several possible functions of a food system science network have been identified for inclusion in the SNA:

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- Function 1 - Knowledge development: The FSS network promotes cocreation and collaboration in carrying out research projects and writing publications, developing knowledge syntheses and proposals for funding.
- Function 2 - Policy engagement: The FSS network promotes science advice for integrated and sectoral food policies based on knowledge syntheses, cocreation on funding mechanisms and with this steer strategic research and innovation agendas through active involvement in policy development and advocacy.
- Function 3 - Education and capacity building: The FSS network promotes education and training to build capacity in food systems science and enhance the knowledge and skills required for food system literacy (Boer, 2021; Huang, 2014).
- Function 4 - Community engagement and outreach: The FSS network promotes the dissemination and brokerage of knowledge via conferences, colleagues and connections to media and society, potentially as part of broader consortia, networks and platforms.
- Function 5 – Business innovation: The FFS network promotes engagement in brokerage and collaboration with businesses for knowledge cocreation and valorisation.

The function business innovation was excluded from the initial research design. It was added based on uniform recommendations of participants on discussions in the first round of results.

Table 1 lists each function along with the associated activities and metric used for assessment of such a function in the survey. The SNA was designed to identify the patterns of collaboration in the FoSSNet community. To enable empirical assessment, each network function was translated into observable activities and corresponding indicators. The analytical framework therefore, links abstract functions, such as knowledge development or policy engagement, to concrete collaborative practices that can be captured in the SNA survey.

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Table 1. Functions, orientation, activity

Function	Orientation	Activity
Knowledge development	Cocreation of research and innovation	Applying for research grant, scientific publications, working in research projects, etc.
Business innovation	Private sector	Collaboration with business in knowledge cocreation and valorisation
Policy engagement	Public policy	Being a member of a science advisory board/steering committee, developing calls for grants, developing/formulating policies, etc.
Education and Capacity Strengthening	Education	Development of education programmes (Bachelors, Masters, Postgraduate diploma programme), Short courses, Tailor made trainings and Refresher courses. etc.
Community engagement and outreach	Communication	Building partnerships, organising events and gatherings, collaborating on engagement platforms (social media, websites), organising stakeholder dialogues or workshops, bringing innovations to the market, etc.

2.3 Data collection & analysis

SNA of Pan-European FoSSNet community

Primary data for the SNA were collected through a survey (designed and administered in the Qualtrics platform) circulated to the FoSSNet community, initially comprised of 63 consortium partner representatives, as well as external participants invited to the first FoSSNet conference held in Oxford in March 2025. Survey distribution started in December 2024 and ended in March 2025, a week after the Oxford conference to allow extra responses from the conference participants.

In the questionnaire, respondents were asked to identify up to five colleagues with whom they most actively collaborate on food system science (FSS) activities. For each named collaboration, follow-up questions captured the type of FSS activities involved and the duration of the relationship. In addition, the questionnaire gathered information on respondents' demographic characteristics, areas of expertise, FSS specialisations, orientations toward research, policy, education, or communication, and their involvement in FSS projects and networks. The questionnaire is presented in Appendix I.

For the national SNAs, a largely identical questionnaire, with some adjustments, was administered during the national feedback workshops. These changes were made to

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address several caveats of the pan-European SNA identified in the Milestone report, including expanding the number of listed connections from 5–10 and incorporating private sector perspectives into the network's functions.

The SNA data at national level were merged with the pan-European SNA to create a larger dataset that not only covers the core FoSSNet members and their connections, but also the FoSSNet key national-level connections and their connections (Table 2).

Table 2. Datasets used for the analysis

Dataset	Number of valid responses
Pan-European FoSSNet SNA survey	76
Netherlands SNA	25
Denmark SNA	15
Germany SNA	14
Latvia SNA	14
United Kingdom SNA	11
Italy SNA	9
Portugal SNA	9
Sweden SNA	8
Spain SNA	7
Belgium SNA	6
France SNA	6
Poland SNA	0
Merged dataset (duplicates removed)	186

There is a clear sampling bias in the data: external conference participants and national workshop participants were recruited by the consortium members of FoSSnet. The sample should not be interpreted as representative of the wider European network of food systems scientists, but rather of the existing project community. Besides, those who attended the workshop and answered the questionnaire were also more likely to be more engaged and committed to the network and its collaborative activities – therefore the results should be interpreted as reflecting the structure and dynamic of a project-centric community, and has limited external validity in terms of representing the broader field of enquiry.

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The merged data was analysed at three levels: the whole network (FoSSNet communities of individuals (“nodes” in the network who are connected via “edges” in the network); cluster (sub-groups) within the network; and the individual position within the network (table 3). Data cleaning, analysis and visualization of the network are done in R. Additionally, similar analyses were performed for the larger national datasets (with at least 10 respondents) to draw comparative insights.

Table 3. Network assessment at 3 levels

Analytical level	Metric	Definition	Insight into network functioning ³
Whole Network	Network Size	Total number of nodes and edges in the network	Scope and scale of the network outlining its reach and complexity
	Density	Proportion of actual connections to possible connections	Level of connectivity: High density suggests stronger inter-node engagement
	Diameter	Length of the longest shortest path between any two nodes in the network	Indicates the maximum distance information must travel; larger diameters suggest more dispersed or fragmented networks
	Average path length	Average number of steps along the shortest paths between all pairs of nodes	Reflects overall efficiency of information flow; shorter paths indicate faster and more cohesive communication
	Transitivity (clustering coefficient)	Proportion of connected node triples that form closed triangles	Indicates the degree of local clustering and cohesion: high transitivity suggests dense, trust-based subgroups with redundant connections; low transitivity points to sparse, broker-dependent structures
Clusters within network	Clusters	Subgroups within the network where nodes are more densely connected internally	Identifies collections of nodes as communities within the network
Individual node positions	Degree centrality	Number of edges a node has	How popular or active a node is
	Betweenness centrality	Frequency a node lies on the shortest path	Control of information flows or a potential information broker

³ Due to the sampling bias discussed above, there could be an overestimation of network density and centralisation, as more peripheral or less engaged actors are likely underrepresented. We come back to these limitations in the Discussion.

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		between two other nodes	
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Structured mapping of thematic scope

To assess how the projects and networks identified through the FoSSNet SNA cover the different dimensions of the food system, we conducted a structured mapping exercise. Projects and networks were first filtered based on salience in the survey data, defined as being mentioned by more than two respondents. These entities were then systematically mapped against the food system framework developed in WP1 and the food system transformation indicators identified in Deliverable 4.1. The resulting analytical matrix (heatmap) comprised rows representing “food system elements,” grouped into four overarching categories derived from the WP1 framework (core food system activities; food system conditions; social and economic conditions; environmental conditions), alongside indicators aligned with the Horizon Europe Strategic Plan 2025–2027 research and innovation gaps and the Food2030 pathways for action.

Each project or network was scored against every food system element using a three-point ordinal scale (1 = no engagement; 2 = partial engagement; 3 = clear engagement), consistent with the scoring logic applied in Deliverable 4.1 to ensure methodological coherence across work packages. Scoring was based on documentary analysis of publicly available project materials, including websites, project descriptions, and implementation reports, to assess the extent to which activities, research objectives, or outputs addressed specific food system elements. The numerical scores were visualized in Excel using conditional formatting (red–yellow–green gradient) to indicate relative levels of engagement. An aggregate row was subsequently calculated to capture the overall coverage of food system elements across all mapped projects and networks, generating a composite heatmap that illustrates areas of concentration and relative gaps within the FoSSNet landscape.

Validation of the European SNA

An initial validation and reflection of the results of the SNA took place during the Oxford Conference, sharing insights with the audience who provided their input and data to the survey. The SNA results were presented as part of a dedicated session focusing on assessing the state of FSS in Europe ([see Milestone report](#)). Following the presentation there was a workshop whereby the conference participants were all split up into break-out rooms. During the break-out rooms sessions a few elevator pitches were given by invited speakers who are involved in a key project or network within FSS. After the elevator pitches the participants were asked to reflect on what they heard, combing the SNA results with the specific elevator pitches. The reflection took place in small groups using a facilitated ORID method (Objective, Reflection, Interpretive, Decisional) (see workshop format in (Appendix II)). They answered questions such as:

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- What are the main objectives and activities of the FSS networks represented here?
- What excites or concerns you most about the current state of FSS networks?
- What gaps, challenges or opportunities do you see in the current network landscape for advancing FSS?
- What are the most important 2-3 actions we can take to strengthen collaboration and impact across FSS networks?

The data of the conference was captured by facilitators who supported the break-out sessions and shared again in a plenary session with all conference participants (see **D6.6 1st Conference proceedings – advancing Food Systems Science** for a summary of these results).

This interactive session gave input to the planned validation through Task 2.2.1 on feedback workshops. The aim of the workshops was to:

- Gain feedback and validate initial EU level SNA results
- Gain insights in national perspectives on FSS Networks
- Collect additional data to make the SNA more robust
- Provide an opportunity for networking at national level

Regarding the workshop participants, there were the following requirements:

- 15-20 people that work in food system science (e.g. from a science, education, policy perspective)
- Invite potential participants both from within your institution and external networks
- Make sure it is a diverse group (career stage, gender, discipline, etc.)

The generic outline of the workshop plan is presented in Table 4. Each country had the freedom to choose whether they would do one or two rounds of gaps discussions. Furthermore, it was up to them and the workshop participants to decide which gaps they would prefer to discuss. Some country workshops also included a discussion about the possibilities for forming a national network (e.g. Belgium, Denmark, the Netherlands, Latvia).

It was decided that partners from the same country would host the workshop together (i.e. the Netherlands, Belgium, Germany), eventually resulting in 12 national feedback workshops. The workshop was to be implemented between July and November 2025. All workshop materials, such as the consent form, PowerPoint presentation, and the canvas were prepared for all countries, in English. It was up to the organisers to decide if this needed translation into their local language. For the workshop in Spain, the organiser created a video that explained the ambition of FoSSNet and the purpose of the SNA in Spanish.

For more details on the feedback workshop preparations, see the guideline in Appendix II.

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Table 4. Schedule for feedback workshops

What	Time	Who	How
Introduction of FoSSNet & workshop	20 mins	Main facilitator	PPT
SNA sharing & validation	60 mins	Main facilitator - presentation (30 mins) Group facilitators - group discussion (30 mins)	PPT & Sheets
Break	20 mins		
Reflection on the Gaps	Option 1: 45 mins Option 2: 75 mins	Group discussion (with facilitators)	Canvas
SNA of the workshop participants (survey)	20 mins	All individually	Survey via QR code
Close	15 mins	Main facilitator	PPT
Total time	3-3,5 hours		

Qualitative analysis of the feedback workshops

The data gathered in each country was reported by the partners in a national feedback workshop report. In those reports, the partners reflected on the process of preparing and executing the workshop and shared the workshop results per identified SNA gap.

The authors of this deliverable reviewed each country report, providing feedback and asking for clarification where needed. When all reports were finalised, the authors collated the raw data, i.e. the national results, per SNA gap. The analysis entailed a general inductive approach (Thomas, 2006) through the identification of common themes between the various countries. This entailed manual coding of the raw data, which was done by one researcher who went through all the national workshop results per gap to identify key themes, which resulted in an initial overview of the EU results per gap. Another researcher then revisited the raw data in combination with the identified themes to verify and adjust these where needed. After the final set of themes had been agreed upon, three researchers continued to expand and adjust the EU level results per gap. This bottom-up iterative process allowed for capturing the essence of

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the national workshops, rather than using a set of predefined codes or themes (Thomas, 2006).

3 Results of the SNA

3.1 Characteristics of FoSSNet communities

Pan-European FoSSNet community

The sample comprised 186 respondents and was characterised by a predominantly mid- to late-career membership. Individuals aged 36-50 formed the largest age group (42.5%), followed by those aged 51-65 (25.8%) (Figure 3). Women made up the majority of the sample (60.8%) (Figure 4). Senior professionals constituted nearly half of the sample (46%), with mid-career (32%) and junior members (22%) also represented (Figure 5). The main professional occupation in the sample is scientist (82%), followed by administrator which includes project manager (4%) (Table 5).

Figure 3. Age group

Figure 4. Respondent gender

Figure 5. Career stage

Table 5. Main occupation

Main occupation	n	%
Scientist	153	82%

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Administrator	8	4%
Civil society representative	4	2%
Policy maker	3	2%
Communicator	2	1%
Private industry representative	2	1%
Programme/Project manager	2	1%
Student	2	1%
Educator/lecturer	2	1%
NA	1	1%
Others	7	4%
Total	186	100%

The FoSSNet community was dominated by scientists who accounted for 82% of the sample, while other professional roles were only marginally represented (Figure 6). It is therefore unsurprising that the community is primarily research-oriented, with the large majority of respondents identifying research as a strong focus of their work (84%). Education also featured prominently, with two-thirds of respondents indicating it as either a moderate (31%) or strong (35%) focus. In contrast, communication and policy engagement were more peripheral functions within the network, most commonly described as moderate areas of activity (47% and 38%, respectively) (Figure 6).

In terms of disciplinary composition, the community drew on a wide range of expertise, with respondents reporting 41 distinct areas of expertise. Social sciences made up the most prominent disciplinary domain (55%), followed by food sciences (29%) and environmental sciences (26%). (Table 6 displays the most represented disciplines). The majority of respondents (69 %) reported expertise in more than one discipline, indicating a substantively multidisciplinary network.

The community's analytical focus on food systems was predominantly integrative (Table 7). Most respondents engaged with research that addresses interactions between three or more food system dimensions, as much as research that focuses on single areas such as activities, drivers and outcomes.

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Figure 6. Focus of work in different areas

Table 6. Most represented disciplines

Discipline	count	% (n = 186)
Social Sciences	103	55%
Food Sciences	54	29%
Environmental Sciences	48	26%
Agricultural Sciences	31	17%
Life sciences	30	16%
Nutrition & Health	24	13%
Applied Systems science	21	11%
Applied sciences	20	11%
Humanities	19	10%
Political Sciences	17	9%
Economics	15	8%
Science Communication	12	6%
Education Innovation	11	6%
Business creation	5	3%

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Physical sciences	5	3%
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Table 7. Food system element focus

Food system elements of focus	count	% (n = 186)
Activities	116	62%
Drivers	115	62%
Outcomes	113	61%
Relationships/interactions between 3 aspects above or more	109	59%
Feedbacks	72	39%
Relationships/interactions between 2 aspects above	68	37%
Other topics ^a	9	5%

Note: ^a Other includes food systems relationship/interaction with other systems, policies, system paradigms, leverage points & lock-ins

Organisationally, the sample of respondents spanned 85 organisations across 16 countries, indicating a high level of institutional and geographical diversity. The United Kingdom (16 organisations), Germany (12 organisations), and the Netherlands (10 organisations) had the largest number of participating organisations, while the Netherlands, Denmark, and Germany contributed the highest numbers of individual respondents (Table 8). There was a clear underrepresentation of Eastern European institutions, with only 4 respondents, which is expected due to Poland’s no-response national survey.

Collaborative relationships substantially extended the boundaries of the network beyond the 186 survey respondents. Through the identification of key collaborators in food system-related work, the network expanded to 870 individual nodes⁴, representing 385 organisations across 35 countries: 26 from Europe, 2 in each of Africa, Asia, North America, South America and 1 from Oceania.

Cross-organisational collaboration was a defining characteristic of the network: 71% of reported ties linked individuals from different organisations. In addition, 39% of these collaborative ties were cross-national, indicating a high degree of international reach within the community. Together, these patterns point to a community characterised by strong boundary-spanning capacity, with extensive potential for knowledge exchange and coordination across organisational and national contexts.

⁴ Note that this is a lower bound of the spread of connections, as respondents were asked to list at most 10 connections with whom they worked the most with on food systems topics, while close to 40% of respondents have more than 10 more contacts to add.

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Table 8. Distribution of organisations and respondents, by country

Country	No of organisations	No of respondents
United Kingdom	16	23
Germany	12	17
Netherlands	10	29
Italy	8	12
Spain	6	17
Latvia	6	15
Belgium	6	13
Sweden	5	12
Denmark	4	20
Portugal	4	10
France	2	7
Poland	2	3
Bosnia and Herzegovina	1	1
Finland	1	1
Ireland	1	1
Switzerland	1	1

Working relationships within the community were relatively recent. Over one third of reported ties (36%) have been established within the past two years, while a further 24% have durations of three to five years and 22% span five to ten years. This suggests a network that was dynamic and expanding, with a substantial proportion of ties formed in the recent past.

As suggested by the dominance of scientists in the sample, patterns of collaboration within the community were strongly skewed towards research-related activities (Table 9). Joint participation in research projects was the most common form of collaboration (66%), followed by co-authoring scientific publications (48%) and collaborating on research grant applications (41%). Communication-oriented collaborations formed a second tier of activity, particularly the co-organisation of events and gatherings (26%) and partnership building (25%), while collaboration via digital platforms was less common (13%). Educational collaborations were present but more limited, with 15% of

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respondents engaged in the development of formal degree programmes and 8% in career training activities. Policy- and private-sector-oriented collaborations were the least prevalent forms of interaction among the respondents and their connections. Only 10% of respondents reported collaboration on policy development or formulation, and fewer than one in ten participated in science advisory boards, steering committees, or private-sector-led stakeholder dialogues. Overall, the table highlights a network that was dense in research collaboration but comparatively weaker in policy engagement, education, and private-sector interaction.

Table 9. Collaboration types

Collaboration types	n	% (n = 915 collaborations)
Research: working in projects together	606	66%
Research: publishing scientific publications	439	48%
Research: applying for research grants	378	41%
Communication: co organised events and gatherings	236	26%
Communication: build partnerships	226	25%
Education: development of bachelors/masters/ postgraduate programmes	138	15%
Communication: collaborate on social media platforms and websites	118	13%
Policy: development formulation of policies	92	10%
Private sector: organise stakeholder dialogues or workshops	76	8%
Education: development of career trainings	75	8%
Policy: members of science advisory board steering committee	65	7%
Private sector: working in projects together	53	6%

Network structure

The reported network of FoSSNet community comprised of 870 nodes connected by 897 collaborative ties, indicating a large but sparsely connected system (network density = 0.0024). Despite this sparsity, the average path length was relatively short (3), indicating that most actors are separated by fewer than three steps. This aligns with earlier findings showing extensive cross-organisational (71%) and cross-national (39%) collaboration, suggesting that boundary-spanning ties help maintain connectivity across the network.

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Within this system, the largest connected component (giant) contained 372 nodes (42%), representing the presence of a core research community embedded within a broader, more fragmented periphery. Density in the giant was slightly higher (0.007), and the average path length within it was ~ 3 with a diameter of 8.5, indicating a relatively navigable core network. The low transitivity (clustering coefficient = 0.071) within the giant confirms that collaborations were predominantly dyadic rather than forming tightly-knit groups. In simpler terms, this means that people who were connected to the same person were not very likely to also be connected to each other. So, tightly knit small groups (where “I work with A who works with B, and I also work with B”) were relatively uncommon across the network. This is consistent with a community oriented towards project-based and research-driven collaboration rather than stable, closed teams.

Figure 7. Visualisation of FoSSNet communities, by colour, bigger nodes have higher degrees, higher weights assigned to ties with longer duration of relationship

Overall, the network structure aligns with earlier evidence of a research-centric, multidisciplinary, and internationally-connected community characterised by brokerage and reach rather than density and cohesion. As illustrated in (Figure 7), information could, in principle, reach most actors via a relatively small core. Peripheral nodes depended on a limited number of actors that served as linking pins to this core to remain connected to the wider network. The dependency reinforces the central role of a small set of highly connected actors (those with higher degrees – higher number of connections) in maintaining overall connectivity (degree: median = 1; mean = 2.49; max = 22). Several noticeably larger nodes were located within or close to the core, as well

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as at a small number of peripheral cluster centres, indicating local hubs within otherwise sparsely connected areas (degree distribution skew). The low density (proportion of actual connections relative to all possible connections), the large number of disconnected subgroups, and the low transitivity (clustering coefficient (proportion of connected node triples that form closed triangles) combined indicate a low cohesion.

Cross-country connections were concentrated among a few central connectors, with a limited number of brokers – individuals characterised by high betweenness centrality (betweenness: median = 0; mean = 868.6; max = 32,770). These brokers facilitated information flow across otherwise weakly connected sub-communities (e.g. country-level communities of researchers who are not direct members of the FoSSNet project). Ties among individuals within the core were generally stronger, as reflected by longer relationship durations, whereas connections at the periphery tended to be less frequent and weaker (supported by low transitivity = 0.048). This structure implies relatively rapid information diffusion within the core of the network, alongside slower and more uneven diffusion towards the network's fringes.

Food System Science Portfolio

Collectively, FoSSNet community members who participated in the SNA surveys were involved in at least 114 food systems science projects⁵, of which 54 (47%) operated at the European scale and 38 (33%) operated at the national scale. In addition, they participated in more than 197 food systems science networks, with 147 of these operating at the European and national scale. This reflects a network with extensive engagement across multiple projects and collaborative platforms.

Identifying thematic clusters of food system science was considered beyond the scope of the SNA survey. As an indicative portfolio analysis, the scale of engagement of the community with the field of inquiry of FSS has been assessed. The heatmap in Figure 8 maps the 22 most mentioned projects and networks - by our SNA respondents - to the field of inquiry of food system science.

Approach of the portfolio evaluation

The underlying data for the heat map are reported in Appendix III. The set of project and networks has been scored, with a 3-point scale, on categories of food system elements derived from the conceptual framework (Ingram et al. 2025) and the mapping of research needs and agendas (Jönsson et al. 2025) of the FoSSNet project. The 3 point scale indicates whether a project/network has no coverage of a food system element with a 1, partial coverage with a 2, and full coverage with a 3. These scores are awarded by reading through the publicly available information of the named projects/networks sourced from their associated online websites. The “About” section, conceptual frameworks and public deliverables were the main documents assessed and used to inform the scoring. To receive a score of 3 the document must specifically mention a food system element or describe work that is within the scope of said element. A score

⁵ In the questionnaire, the respondents were given a definition of food systems science. The projects and networks they mention should relate to this definition.

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of 2 is awarded if an element is not specifically mentioned but the activities outlined affect an element indirectly or are focusing on elements adjacent which are somewhat overlapping. Lastly a score of 1 is given if the documents make no reference to a food system element and in addition the named activities have no adjacency or overlap that could indicate partial coverage. The heatmap should be interpreted as an aggregate indication of thematic coverage within the portfolio of projects and networks nominated by SNA respondents, rather than as an evaluation of performance or impact. Total scores reflect the cumulative presence of engagement across projects for a given food system element; higher totals therefore indicate broader portfolio-level coverage, not depth or quality of intervention. Conversely, lower scores signal areas where relatively few respondent-nominated projects explicitly engage with that domain. Importantly, the results reflect the observed network landscape emerging from the SNA survey and therefore represent how respondents perceive and interact with the food system. Identified “gaps” should thus be understood as gaps in network connectivity and representation within this mapped portfolio, rather than definitive absences within the broader European food systems research ecosystem.

Figure 8. Heatmap of the FoSSNet community's project and network research areas mapped to the elements of the food system conceptual framework.

Note: Green shades indicate higher than average coverage and red shades indicate lower than average coverage. Darker intensity represents a higher (green) or lower (red) frequency by which the element is addressed in the project portfolio. Data source: Appendix III.

Results

Across the 22 projects/networks nominated by SNA respondents, FoSSNet's “observed” portfolio shows its strongest and most consistent coverage in governance-, policy-, and innovation-oriented food system work, rather than in biophysical/environmental domains (Figure 8). The highest-scoring food system elements are technological and social innovation (≈ 60), policy & governance (≈ 57), and several governance-related indicators such as food systems governance and policy (≈ 53), governance systems & power dynamics (≈ 53), and governance for food systems change (≈ 56). In the “Food2030 pathways” block, nutrition and sustainable healthy diets is also strongly represented (≈ 57). At the group level, the portfolio is most aligned with the Horizon Europe Strategic Plan 2025–2027 R&I gaps (mean ≈ 2.07 , with $\sim 41\%$ of all cells scored “Yes”), indicating that respondents primarily anchor the network in R&I agendas that emphasise transformation levers (governance, innovation, and systems approaches) and diet/health-oriented pathways.

By contrast, the heatmap indicates systematic under-coverage (in the respondent-nominated set) for environmental conditions and several “foundational conditions” themes. The environmental conditions group is the clearest gap: it has the lowest mean score (≈ 1.35) and the highest share of “No” scores ($\sim 75\%$), suggesting the portfolio is not (yet) strongly connected at least via respondents' nominated projects to work explicitly spanning biosphere/hydrosphere/atmosphere/geosphere framing. Additional low-coverage areas include the microbiome world (≈ 26 , lowest single item), animal welfare, antimicrobial resistance, media, investments, labour skills & availability,

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geopolitical process & context, and food systems Africa (all typically ≈ 1.2 – 1.36 on average). We have mapped the overall scores on the FS framework to make it easier to visualise and interpret these results with circles over the food system elements, which are shaded greener to indicate higher coverage and red for lower coverage (figure 8).

Substantively, this implies a portfolio that is currently stronger on governance and innovation narratives of transformation than on biophysical/environmental systems coverage and certain political-economy and capability constraints. We can interpret these as priority domains where FoSSNet may wish to (i) recruit additional nodes/partner networks, (ii) create targeted bridging activities, or (iii) explicitly signal as “known gaps” in the SNA-informed mapping (i.e., gaps in what respondents surfaced, not necessarily gaps in Europe as a whole).

National-level FoSSNet communities

To explore how collaboration networks differ across FoSSNet partner countries, we analysed the survey results from countries with at least ten valid responses and an 80% response rate⁶. The results reveal substantial variation in how collaborative networks were structured.

In most countries, the networks were characterised by a central component formed around longer-term collaborative relationships. Germany was the notable exception: it showed no central component, with respondents indicating individual, non-overlapping connections. This fragmentation suggested that the feedback workshops succeeded in engaging participants beyond the “usual suspects,” – those who are used to working more closely together, while also highlighting opportunities to strengthen connections so that information and knowledge could circulate more effectively within the network.

Among countries with central components, the Netherlands and Denmark showed a clear international orientation, with nodes in the central component originating from outside their own country, while others displayed a more nationally focused structure.

Across all five workshops, participation was dominated by scientists, with only a small number of policymakers and no representation from the private sector. In terms of disciplinary backgrounds, Germany stood out as having the most diverse range of fields beyond the social sciences; the most participants identified agricultural sciences, food science, nutrition and health, life sciences, and science communication as their areas of expertise. Although the small sample size limits the ability to draw strong correlations, this disciplinary diversity may help explain the more disconnected network structure observed among German respondents.

Regarding collaboration ties, the country-level networks aligned broadly with the pan-European picture: research remained the most common basis for collaboration. The second most common collaboration mode varied slightly by country. In the German and

⁶ Computed as the number of survey responses over number of workshop attendants.

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UK samples, communication and partnership-building were relatively prominent among collaborative activities. In Latvia, private-sector-led stakeholder dialogues or workshops ranked above education-related activities, whereas in the UK private-sector involvement ranked below education activities such as curriculum development.

Figure 9. Social network of Dutch workshop participants (25 responses - 165 nodes in the network)

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Figure 10. Social network of German workshop participants (14 responses - 59 nodes)

Figure 11. Social network of Latvian workshop participants (14 responses - 59 nodes)

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Figure 12. Social network of Danish workshop participants (15 responses - 91 nodes)

Figure 13. Social network of UK workshop participants (11 responses - 94 nodes)

3.2 Vulnerabilities and Gaps in the network

The network shows signs of being potentially “hub-driven,” with a small number of individuals exhibiting significantly higher connections than the rest. These highly connected individuals, who are typically senior researchers or scientists with strong, long-standing ties, play a critical role in sustaining communication across the network (Figure 14). However, this also introduces vulnerability: if these hubs become overloaded, disengaged, or removed, the network risks fragmentation and a sharp decline in its overall reach. Such dependence can create unequal influence, reinforcing power imbalances and reducing the resilience of the wider community.

Before: full graph (top 5% by betweenness highlighted)

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Figure 14. Betweenness centrality highlighted

A related structural issue concerns the presence of bottleneck nodes that act as bridges between national or institutional research communities. In several countries, entire subcommunities are connected to the broader network through only a few individuals. These nodes function as single points of failure; if they leave the network or reduce their involvement, entire groups risk becoming isolated. This pattern is confirmed in the stress-test results, where removing the top 5% of nodes by betweenness centrality leads to the collapse of the giant component (Figure 15). Cross-community links largely disappear, long-range ties become sparse, and clusters that were previously near the centre become fully disconnected. These individuals were therefore structural bottlenecks, and their removal would cause communication to become siloed within small, fragmented groups. This is indicative of a fragile assemblage centred around key actors, rather than a resilient, distributed pan-European community.

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After: top 5% by betweenness nodes removed (same layout coordinates)

Figure 15. Betweenness centrality removed

The limited number of cross-community links also raises the potential for “echo chambers,” where country-based clusters have far more internal than external connections. This reduces the flow of knowledge, campaigns, and innovation across the network and risks confining ideas within tightly knit groups.

Another significant gap – or rather an inherent bias of FoSSNet - lies in the heavy concentration around research activities as the main mode of collaboration. To fully support science, innovation, and food system transformation, FoSSNet would benefit from strengthening ties in underrepresented collaboration areas such as education, communication, policy engagement, and private-sector partnerships.

Stakeholder diversity is also limited. The network is dominated by researchers and scientists, with only minimal participation from policymakers, educators, communication specialists, and—the most notable omission—the private sector. This restricts the network’s capacity to cocreate actionable solutions and reduces the potential for impact.

Although some interdisciplinarity is present, disciplines beyond the social and food sciences remain underrepresented. Although this bias towards social sciences came from the original partnership construction of the FoSSNet consortium, actively engaging participants from fields such as life sciences, nutrition, agricultural sciences, and science communication would enrich the network’s knowledge base and broaden its problem-solving capacity.

The role of early career researchers (ECRs) also appears constrained. Despite FoSSNet’s ambition to elevate their involvement and support their networking, ECRs remain predominantly engaged in research-only collaborations. They are more likely to work with colleagues within their own organisations and participate in fewer types of

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collaborative activities, limiting their exposure to broader communities and diverse forms of knowledge exchange.

Finally, the network shows uneven geographical representation. It is dominated by participants from Northern and Western Europe, while Southern and Eastern Europe remain significantly underrepresented. This imbalance limits its ability to reflect the diverse realities of food system science across Europe.

4 Feedback workshop results

The feedback workshops were held in 12 partner countries. They varied in the type and number of participants, and the gaps they analysed as can be seen in Table 10. In total there were 148 workshop participants, varying from 22 people in a hybrid workshop in Poland to seven people in an in-person meeting in the UK. We also saw differences in the types of attendees, while most partners invited a broad range of people (from research, government, private sector, public sector), in a lot of occasions the workshop participants were only, or mainly, researchers and academics from their own institutes or from institutions the organising partner connects with. Attention was paid, however, to get at least diversity across disciplines, age and seniority level and gender across all invited workshop participants, including the attending researchers.

As outlined in section 2 the data collection and the workshop program left some flexibility in terms of the amount of time spent on discussing the network gaps identified through the SNA. Furthermore, there was freedom for the workshop organisers and the workshop participants to choose the gaps of their interest. As Table 11 shows, in four workshops all the gaps were discussed, while three workshops covered at most three gaps. The coverage of gaps was poorly predicted by the number of participants, or organisers' familiarity with the gaps. Uneven geographical coverage (Gap 6) was least of interest, an indication that this gap was not prioritised equally across the workshop organisers or participants.

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Table 10. Overview of workshop participants per country

Country	Number of participants	Number of facilitators	Format	Type of participants
Belgium, BE	11	4	In person	Mixed: researchers, EU government, private sector
Denmark, DK	12	5	Hybrid	Only researchers
France, FR	8	1	In person	Only researchers
Germany, DE	15	5	Online	Mixed: researchers and research administration
Italy, IT	11	2	Online	Mixed: researchers, National and local government, a farmer
Latvia, LV	13	3	In person	Only researchers
Poland, PL	22	1-2	Hybrid	Mixed: researchers, government, NGOs
Portugal, PT	12	3	In person	Only researchers
Spain, ES	10	2	In person	Only researchers
Sweden, SE	8	4	In person	Only researchers
Netherlands, NL	19	6	In person	Mixed: researchers, NGOs
United Kingdom, UK	7	3	In person	Only researchers
Total:	148	38		

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Table 11. Overview of discussed gaps per country

Country	Gap 1 Lack of bridges between and within communities	Gap 2 Vulnerable hub-driven network	Gap 3 Lack of collaboration beyond research	Gap 4 Limited engagement beyond academia	Gap 5 Limited role of earlier career researchers	Gap 6 Uneven geographical coverage	Total
Belgium, BE		x	x	x	x	x	5
Denmark, DK				x	x		2
France, FR	x	x	x	x	x	x	6
Germany, DE	x				x	x	3
Italy, IT	x						1
Latvia, LV	x	x	x				3
Poland, PL	x	x	x	x	x	x	6
Portugal, PT	x	x	x	x	x	x	6
Spain, ES		x	x	x		x	4
Sweden, SE	x	x		x	x		4
Netherlands, NL	x	x	x	x	x		5
United Kingdom, UK	x	x	x	x	x	x	6
Total:	9	9	8	9	9	7	

4.1 Gap 1 – Lack of bridges between and within communities

4.1.1 Understanding the gap

In this section, the results of the 12 country-level workshops are presented to indicate how the gaps identified in the SNA survey are understood, how they could be closed, and what recommendations are developed to this effect. In the presentation of results, the country codes in the Tables 10 and 11 are used to refer to the country-level workshops and its participants.

Several country-level participant groups identified that one of the biggest barriers that causes a lack of bridges between and within communities is the lack of multidisciplinary, often referred to a silos or silo mentality. Path dependency and distinct scientific cultures make it difficult to identify and reach across these silos to suitable peers (PT).

One of the reasons for absent or limited multidisciplinary is the "mismatch of incentives", i.e. recruitment committees, scientific journals, and the evaluation of metrics often remain strictly monodisciplinary, punishing those who spend time building bridges between disciplines and actor groups (FR, PL, IT, UK).

Furthermore, there is the lack of dedicated resources to support interdisciplinary research, specifically time and long-term funding were cited as the reason why connections remain transactional, project-based, and focused on parts of the system rather than the whole (DE, IT, PT, UK). This is further exacerbated by geographical asymmetries in resource access, including resources needed for community building, particularly when the physical distances within countries that limit engagement of researchers (PT, UK).

Additionally, there is also a universal recognition that "language" acts as a major friction point; the jargon of specialized research creates a barrier to connect to other disciplines, making the translation of ideas time-consuming and exhausting (DE, IT, PT, PL, UK). This can be coupled with the suggestion made during the Swedish workshop that researchers often operate under the delusion that their specific field represents the entire system rather than a small part of it (SE). Researchers hence operate within certain "opinion corridors" and disciplinary bubbles (SE, NL), and fail to look beyond disciplines towards sectors, for example (UK). This also stems from variation in food system literacy within and among groups of researchers and other stakeholders (PT).

Beyond the interdisciplinarity there are also challenges with transdisciplinarity, mainly in the realm of stakeholder engagement. Here incentives, resource constraints, and the language were also viewed as barriers to connect with the private sector. Researchers lack the professional incentives to prioritize "tangible results" over academic papers (IT,UK); second, a fundamental lack of shared language, acronym-heavy communication (IT, DE, PT, PL); and third, there are data privacy concerns and a lack of long-term,

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transversal funding (IT, DE, PT, NL) which prevent the creation of stable, mutually beneficial relationships. This all accumulates in a lack of trust between academia and practitioners. In the Italian workshop it was mentioned that there is a "sense of distrust" from private sector and civil society actors who feel exploited for data without receiving tangible benefits. Latvia, on the other hand presented an outlier case of success, noting a strong existing synergy between industry and academia that is less prevalent in Western European counterparts.

Finally, as a counter-narrative to this gap, participants in the Dutch workshop questioned whether high modularity is inherently negative and suggesting that specialization can foster resilience if "orchestrators" bridge gaps effectively.

4.1.2 Closing the gap

To close the identified gaps, several common strategies emerged across the country-level workshops. Strategies relate to stakeholder engagement, for example by tailoring the communication to move beyond academic jargon, ensuring that messages resonate with diverse stakeholders such as farmers, industry, and policy makers (DE, IT, PT, UK). There is also a need for simplifying bureaucratic hurdles for the private sector and civil society to engage, to ensure that ground-up, citizen-driven initiatives and vulnerable groups are actively integrated into research agendas (IT, PT, UK).

To deal with the silo mentality consensus exists on the need for structural support for interdisciplinarity, specifically through the creation of scientific journals that actively promote interdisciplinary research (FR, PL) and the provision of earmarking funds or structural support for cross-sectoral networks (IT, SE, PL).

Countries also highlighted the importance of creating intentional spaces for dialogue both between researchers and beyond research. Such as facilitated informal exchanges, summer schools, or methodical biweekly meetings, to build the trust and "systems language" necessary for lasting collaboration (IT, NL, LV). Participants in Sweden emphasized the need for post-meeting follow-ups and those in The Netherlands warned against making networks too large, suggesting instead that "binding perspectives" from inspirational speakers are more effective than simple expert gatherings. Participants in Germany furthermore advocated for the use of professional communication agencies and "multipliers" to bridge the gap between research and funding bodies.

4.2 Gap 2 – Vulnerable hub-driven network

4.2.1 Understanding the gap

In understanding the gaps two main issues were identified. The first issue has to do with the size of the organisation. The hub tends to be a larger organisation, or a person working for a larger organisation. This is often where the available funding and influence come together. Regarding funding it often seems that evaluators favour established,

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"well-known names" to minimize perceived risk, as funders gravitate towards established excellence and lack interest to look at ideas outside of the norms (LV, PL, NL, SE, UK). Thus, institutions with the capacity to design and lead projects often become central hubs in the network, reinforcing their influence (ES).

This also implies that smaller organisations tend to normally be involved in "secondary roles" because they lack the administrative capacity and "reputation" required to lead large-scale projects (LV, PL, BE). These countries linked this gap with Gap 6: Uneven geographical coverage and emphasized regional and administrative disparities, noting that smaller entities in Central and Eastern Europe do much of the substantive work, but they mostly remain as "implementing partners". The smaller organisations are also more at risk as they depend on these senior researchers or prestigious universities acting as hubs, and if they withdraw, as hubs tend to be a temporary structure (UK), the smaller organisations can become isolated and relationships broken down, leaving smaller partners without a path to influence (FR, PL). Participants in the UK added that a hub-driven network also tends to overlook new entrants.

It was however noted that this plays out at the European level, where power and visibility tend to be concentrated in a relatively small number of institutions and countries. In contrast, at the local level, networks appear to be more horizontally distributed, with a wider variety of actors involved and a more even balance of influence (ES).

Second, it was highlighted how "personality," "charisma," and the "individual genius" myth in academic culture allow certain figures to dominate (SE, NL), cultivating egos and opportunistic behaviour (BE). These often tend to be senior males, who have benefitted from the 'traditional' academic systems (BE), i.e. the hierarchical, competitive and individual-centred structures in academia (SE). This also connects to the gap Limited role of early career researchers (Gap 5), as in the Netherlands it was pointed out that junior colleagues are paid to "do the work" and they must prove themselves before they can be granted access to certain meetings and positions.

Some countries furthermore explicitly linked Gap 1: Lack of bridges between and within communities and Gap 2, arguing that the absence of disciplinary bridges forces the network to rely on a few "individual geniuses" who act as the sole translators between sectors (FR, PL, SE). Participants in Portugal offered a unique observation on "agenda-setting," noting that hubs eventually drift from being research actors to becoming "deciders of exclusion." The existence of hubs is not necessarily negative, if their attitude is positive and their values make their impact on agenda setting inclusive and aware of possible asymmetries.

4.2.2 Closing the gap

To close the gap of vulnerable, hub-driven networks, a clear consensus emerged around the necessity of a generational and structural transfer of social capital. Across workshops it was emphasised that senior researchers must move beyond being

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"gatekeepers" to becoming active facilitators who delegate responsibilities and co-represent projects with junior researchers, a strategy intended to both reduce expert burnout and empower newcomers (FR, PL, NL, BE).

This shift was supported by the idea that funding should be used as a primary policy instrument to dilute the "hub effect" and expand the network nodes, with suggestions for specific quota and measures to include peripheral regions and less-represented countries (PT, SE, PL). Furthermore, there was a shared belief that networks like FoSSNet should adopt formal governance structures, such as policy working groups and standardized impact monitoring, to ensure that inclusion is a built-in requirement rather than an informal choice (SE, UK).

For participants in the Central and Eastern European countries, Latvia and Poland, closing the gap is a matter of overcoming geographical "prestige" barriers by building a reputation through reliable, niche specialization to force Western hubs into more equitable partnerships. Other workshop participants deduced that "if we fix Gap 5 and Gap 6, then we end up fixing Gap 2" (BE).

Participants in France and Poland proposed that the loss of a major hub can be viewed as a positive opportunity for "de-concentration," forcing the network to rebuild more resilient, horizontal connections. In line with this idea of resilient horizontal connections participants argued that hubs must be fundamentally "re-rooted" in local realities and the public sphere to remain relevant (ES), while it was also suggested to diversify the network beyond academia to include entrepreneurs and social enterprises (UK). Ultimately, these solutions suggest that the goal is to transform hubs from points of vulnerability into robust "gateways" that allow the best ideas to flourish regardless of their origin (SE, UK).

4.3 Gap 3 – Lack of collaboration beyond research

4.3.1 Understanding the gap

Participants widely recognized that cross-sectoral cooperation is hindered by a lack of incentives for researchers, the misalignment of interests with other sectors and lack of a common language. (PL, ES, NL, LV).

A primary barrier is the academic incentive system, which doesn't actively encourage and support engagement beyond academia. Recruitment, promotion, and funding evaluate disciplinary scientific productivity (e.g., number of papers, PhDs) rather than societal impact and sustained collaboration with diverse stakeholders (UK, NL, PT, FR). This results in a reliance on personal motivation, often in conflict with institutional culture, and makes interdisciplinary or transdisciplinary work a non-attractive career choice (ES, PT, BE).

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This incentive mismatch reinforces the divergence in research focus and outputs. Research is often perceived as addressing topics in a way that they don't respond to societal or market needs, producing solutions difficult to apply under real-world conditions (PL, PT). Consequently, projects can become disconnected from daily practices and lived realities within food systems (ES).

A second barrier is difficulty to engage different stakeholders since different groups of actors operate in different visions, guided by their own goals, constraints, language and logic of action (PL). In particular, relationships with the private sector are often narrowly focused, shaped by contractual and publishing restrictions, and can be skewed by power dynamics where larger institutions negotiate better terms (NL, BE, UK).

In most workshops, participants also identified the lack of common language between sectors as another reason for weak cross-sectoral cooperation. Researchers often lack training in communication, stakeholder engagement, and policy processes, leaving them without the know-how to translate findings into accessible messages or navigate different organizational cultures and problem-solving attitudes (UK, PT, BE). Furthermore, differing objectives, funding schemes, and timescales—short-term research projects versus long-term systemic change or rapid policy/business cycles—create persistent friction (NL).

4.3.2 Closing the gap

To close the gap different strategies emerged focused on alignment of incentives, redesign of models for collaboration and strengthening communication. In relation to incentives, a change in the academic culture is required to move from a focus on competition and deliverables to one of openness, trust, and shared networks (NL). Institutions should review how researchers are evaluated, moving beyond patents and papers toward metrics that measure real impact of research on society (PT, UK).

To address real-world needs, models such as agroecological living labs and learning networks were suggested to be promising structures for place-based knowledge cocreation, ensuring that diverse actors are meaningfully involved at all stages of the research process (ES, NL, FR). Dedicating roles and resources to the facilitation of dialogue was suggested as a mechanism to facilitate and support inter- and transdisciplinary processes (ES). Communication is considered instrumental in targeting and facilitating engagement among different types and levels of stakeholders.

Finally, addressing power dynamics is key to meaningful engagement. This requires acknowledging and deliberately managing power imbalances in collaborations, for instance through funding schemes that specifically target less powerful societal actors (NL, UK). Motivating private sector participation hinges on transparent rules, clear mutual benefits, and realistic expectations (PL).

4.4 Gap 4 – Limited engagement beyond academia

4.4.1 Understanding the gap

In understanding this gap, two main issues were discussed. The first concerns the engagement of societal actors. Researchers, civil society, policymakers, and the private sector often operate on parallel paths with divergent objectives, working methods, timelines, and definitions of innovation (ES, FR, PL). This creates a fundamental misalignment where research agendas and project designs rarely originate from or respond to the articulated needs of these groups (NL, PL).

From several countries, the evidence is that engagement with civil society is very limited, risking a research agenda driven by knowledge-driven interests rather than societal values – vulnerable groups and their interests are consistently underrepresented in science networks (FR, PL, NL). This causes the perception that research does not respond to societal needs – as also discussed in gap 3. Weak public communication could reinforce this effect and foster a perception of food system transformation as a process imposed "from above" (PL).

The collaboration with the private sector was also discussed as a structural barrier, including conflicts over intellectual property from publicly funded research, high financial stakes, and a fundamental mismatch in both timelines (slow public research vs. business deadlines) and the definition of innovation (long-term systemic change vs. quick, incremental solutions) (FR, PL, UK). These differences often reduce partnerships to transactional relationships, further hindered by data protection concerns (UK).

Furthermore, collaboration with policymakers is constrained by a deeply entrenched silo mentality within government structures. Participants noted that different ministries (e.g., agriculture, health, climate) often operate independently, leading to mismatched narratives and competition between policy areas. The result is a lack of access for researchers to the policy cycle and a persistent difficulty in communicating the relevance of research in a way that aligns with the timing and specific needs of policymakers (SE, UK).

The second issue is related to academic incentives and a silo mentality – also linked to the discussion from gap 3 and gap 1 - which discourage researchers from looking beyond their own disciplines. Current academic systems prioritize individual outputs, such as publications, over practice-oriented or collaborative efforts (ES, PL). This culture is reinforced by a lack of intermediaries capable of bridging scientific language into contexts where societal actors can engage on their own terms (NL, PL). Even when practitioners or students are included, their roles often remain "declarative" or marginal within formally constructed project networks (DK, PL).

4.4.2 Closing the gap

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To bridge the divide between academia and society, strategies must focus on knowledge cocreation and structural reform. Research questions should not be predefined in silos but codesigned with diverse actors to reflect real-world needs (ES, SE). This shift requires moving beyond project stakeholders to building reciprocal, long-term relationships where social actors contribute to both the research agenda and final insights (ES, SE).

Addressing the time and resource barrier requires a shift in academic infrastructure. Highlighting the role of research coordinators or facilitators (a role that already exist in the private sector) can allow researchers to focus on science while experts manage the networking and bridge-building (SE, ES). To support this, academic incentives must be reformed to reward inter- and transdisciplinary efforts, particularly for early-career researchers, while government-led incentives can better align private sector goals with public research (ES, FR).

Communication remains a central pillar to close this gap. The creation of a common language is essential, supported by policy labs and education modules that raise food system literacy across all sectors (PT). Tailoring communication through segmented newsletters, media engagement, and the use of translational people ensures that scientific evidence is accessible and relevant to policymakers and practitioners (BE, UK). By treating relationship-building as a core network function, the network can establish the credible governance and trust needed for sustained, multi-actor collaboration (BE, DK).

4.5 Gap 5 – Limited role of earlier career researchers

4.5.1 Understanding the gap

There was broad consensus across almost all workshop that this gap should be understood in the context of structural and institutional barriers, rather than a lack of interest. Early-career researchers (ECR) are forced into a "bibliometric trap". Performance metrics that focus on publication output and individual "box-checking" are discouraging young researchers from investing time in networking and interdisciplinary collaboration (DE, PT, PL, SE, BE). This is also related to the issue of access and visibility, where ECRs must already be part of a network to be invited into the informal circles where critical debates happen and opportunities are shared (DK, PL, NL).

Furthermore, there was a shared recognition of the precarity and resource constraints for ECRs. Between short-term contracts, high mobility expectations, and the heavy trade-offs between research, teaching and administration, many ECRs can perceive networking as an "invisible" or "additional" burden they cannot afford (DK, DE, UK, PL, SE) or prioritize, especially when its benefits of are not clearly visible or communicated (BE). Finally, the role of senior academics as gatekeepers was emphasized; ECRs are

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often dependent on their supervisors' mindset and willingness to "invite them in" or delegate coordination tasks to gain any institutional leverage (DK, SE, NL, PL).

While across workshops there was agreement on the systemic pressures facing ECRs, the interpretations of the gap differ: perspectives ranged from viewing it as an inevitable professional stage to a critical structural failure. Participants questioned whether this is truly a "gap" at all, suggesting that the lower visibility of ECRs may simply reflect a natural phase of career progression and shorter time in the system, rather than a specific deficit (FR, PL). To determine whether this gap reflects a "natural career stage" or actual systemic barriers, it was emphasized that more in depth-analysis is needed (for example, automatic examination of publication co-authorship networks or analysis of correlations between seniority and the number and strength of network connections).

In other workshops, participants identified deep cultural and psychological barriers that hinder growth. The impact of "imposter syndrome" and a hierarchical culture that often treats junior scientists as staff paid to "do the work" rather than as potential leaders, creating an environment where young researchers feel they must "prove themselves" before they are worthy of networking (NL, BE). The low-salary nature of the food sector creates a dual pressure: researchers are trapped by academic metrics but find few rewarding opportunities in the private sector to justify leaving (PL, PT). Lack of intellectual ownership of junior researchers implies they rarely have access to their own funding lines to lead independent projects (UK). There are specific mobility barriers inherent in the modern academic market, where the expectation to move abroad often conflicts with the need to maintain stable professional networks during a high-pressure career phase (DE).

4.5.2 Closing the gap

Ensuring engagement ECRs was considered important in view of the new ideas they contribute and methodological innovations, including digital skills and early adoption of AI. Future generations are likely to be the ones to drive systemic change (UK, PT). Participants across workshops proposed several ways to address the gap around ECRs involvement in food system science.

There was broad consensus across workshops on the need for structured junior-senior integration. Instead of leaving networking to chance, participants proposed formal mentorship schemes (DE, UK, NL, BE, DK). There was also strong agreement on the need for dedicated financial and logistical support for ECRs. This includes dedicated funding for network participation, pre-events at conferences to build confidence, and ensuring that ECR involvement is a formal, funded requirement in project planning rather than a voluntary choice (NL, DE, DK, PL).

In addition, there was a shared emphasis on broadening the skill set of ECRs beyond research alone. Networks should promote senior academics support for ECRs in grant writing, coordination and communication skills that are essential for career progression but often missing from disciplinary PhD programs (DK, PT, UK, DE). A paradigm shift is required in evaluation scientific impact, moving away from bibliometric traps toward

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qualitative assessments (e.g., CoARA) that reward networking and societal impact (DE, PT, PL, UK).

The need for structured support was identified across workshops. The solutions proposed differed, which reflected distinct philosophies regarding how to integrate junior researchers into the network. From an orientation on the realities of the researcher across life stages, there was advocacy for fellowship schemes and the formal inclusion of social security and fair working conditions as non-negotiable requirements in project planning (DE). A priority on the behavioural and social environment, resulted in a plea for safe spaces and targeted pre-events that explicitly facilitate senior-junior interactions to lower complexity of access/entry (NL). In contrast, a more self-driven approach would encourage that ECRs are enabled to lead their own communities of practice, producing alternative outputs like podcasts and seminars rather than just academic papers (BE, UK). Instead of positive discrimination that artificially levels the playing field, fostering a culture where young researchers can build agency naturally without the pressure of forced, declarative performance metrics (PL). From the viewpoint on the insecurity of young researchers in the job market, a systems approach should concentrate on ensuring that new professional roles exist in society to absorb a new generation of professionals and specific skills (digital native generation) (PT).

4.6 Gap 6 – Uneven geographical coverage

4.6.1 Understanding the gap

The analysis of the gap “Uneven geographical coverage” across the participating countries highlights clear structural and historical roots behind the geographical imbalance in food system science networks. Participants from Spain, Belgium and Poland noted that Western European institutions benefit from a historical head start, creating a self-reinforcing cycle where existing resources, contacts and “centrality” in networks attract further funding. Differences in national R&D investment and GDP also contribute to disparities, shaping the size and strength of local research communities (FR, PT, PL). For example, participants in France pointed out that regions with larger populations and bigger economies tend to have stronger research communities. Differences in GDP and the percentage of GDP spent on research make it “natural” for some regions to be more active in research than others.

Furthermore, a critical participant shared concern emerged regarding structural barriers and “tokenism” toward Eastern Europe. Even when funding opportunities exist, they are often too narrow or treat Eastern European partners as “checkbox” participants rather than intellectual leaders (BE, DE, PL). This is exacerbated by divergent research agendas: while Western Europe focuses on post-CAP (Common Agricultural Policy) transitions, sustainability and health, Eastern European contexts may prioritize production and food security, leading to a mismatch where Western theoretical frameworks are “imposed” on local realities (UK, DE).

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The mobility of researchers was another factor mentioned, where the lack of stable local positions forces talent to move West, simultaneously weakening national capacity while acting as the only remaining bridge for international connectivity through personal links (FR, DE, PL).

Participants in Spain and Portugal argued that local scientific capacity is strong since they have high-quality, systemic food research. However, this work remains "invisible" because it is published in local languages or uses different terms that don't conceptually align with the food system science as it is developed in EU projects (ES, PT).

Eastern European countries face additional challenges, as highlighted for Poland: Eastern countries are often used as "testing grounds" for Western concepts (e.g., multifunctionality or land-use reduction) that do not fit the Polish reality of small-scale farming. It was also mentioned that there is a "time barrier" for academics since in Poland 80% of the academic work is devoted to teaching, leaving small space for international networking which often means unpaid time and travel (the opposite is observed in Belgium). A perception among participants was that some research leaders from Western Europe doubt the capacity of an Eastern European coordinator to "deliver".

4.6.2 Closing the gap

The results revealed a shared understanding across workshops that the geographical gap in FSS is not accidental, but the result of structural disparities and regional differences in Europe. To address this gap, several strategies were proposed.

There was a shared call for strategic mobility. There is need to move beyond "brain drain" and toward "knowledge circulation". Target researchers to build long-term, cross-border collaborations fosters the individual scientist and cements relations between science institutions (DK, DE, ES, FR). Mobility strategies should be complemented with stronger outreach activities in underrepresented regions and using local hubs or satellite clusters that can serve as connectors to broader networks (PT). A contrasting approach is to bridge the existing East-West divide through established large-scale project cooperation rather than through creating new, localized clusters (DE, DK).

Some groups proposed more targeted structural interventions. Radical, interventionist approaches such as "positive discrimination" and "targeted funding" for underrepresented actors (BE, PT). Others placed emphasis on working within existing frameworks like Horizon Europe or "natural" drivers like researcher mobility (DK, FR).

For some, the focus should be on capacity building, networking and matchmaking also suggesting training in bid-writing (BE, UK). Others called for solutions that go deeper into the root causes of structural disparities (ES, PL). No amount of bid-writing training can solve the heavy teaching load in Poland; their implicit need is for a solution that addresses the institutional framework of the university itself.

Finally, practical barriers to inclusion can be overcome. Using AI and new technologies was suggested to reduce the language barriers, seeing it as a tool for inclusivity (PL).

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Alternatively, more "people-centered" approaches could entail investing in the skills and opportunities for specific individuals with existing cross-regional links or for the younger generations to act as bridge-builders and agents of change (DE, UK).

5 Conclusions and recommendations

5.1 Conclusions

The findings from the study provide insights for delivering on the European Research Area (ERA) for food systems and the Next-Generation Roadmap for Food Systems Science (Lopez et al. 2025). The ERA promotes excellent science in full interplay with society. The roadmap proposes that FSS in Europe should be rooted in multi-level, multi-actor, and flexible frameworks that recognize the interconnectedness of local, regional, national, and EU-wide priorities.

The SNA data, which covers a network to 870 individuals across 385 organisations in 35 countries, suggests how collaboration is structured across scales and how this may shape future trajectories of food systems science. Members who participated in the SNA are involved in projects that mostly operate at European scale and national scale, indicating strong activity at supranational and domestic levels. Networking at EU-wide level has benefited strongly from investments over the past years, and several selected European projects operate as hubs for the food systems research community. However, the network structure shows a clear core-periphery pattern, with a small set of highly connected actors driving most connectivity and linking otherwise separate clusters. This suggests that cross-scale integration currently depends on a limited number of bridging actors rather than being structurally embedded across the network. This concentration raises questions about longer-term resilience and continuity should these actors disengage. Achterbosch and Bogaardt (2021) have documented that the uptake of insights from food system research into EU level decision-making is a multifaceted process that involves a flow of ideas through a web of informal and formal expert groups in the science-policy-society interface. Ensuring systematic lessons learned are documented and integrated into EU-level programming is critical. If knowledge flows between national initiatives and EU-level processes rely heavily on a small number of well-connected individuals or organisations, there is a risk that insights remain person-dependent rather than institutionally embedded.

The SNA participant network and projects, which we used for the heatmap, give us an indication of the level of topic alignment with overarching framework and policy objectives at the EU level. Regarding the Horizon Europe Strategic plan, coverage of

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technological and social innovation is strong and is supported by broad international cooperation. Food system governance and complex food system interactions are key focus areas; however, there is scope to include more projects and networks addressing biodiversity, ecosystems, and water resilience. This aligns with the overall mapping findings, which suggest that FoSSNet communities remain only loosely connected to the fundamental sciences and that discussions on the natural science aspects of food systems research are underdeveloped or insufficiently highlighted in this exercise.

The FoSSNet community is strongly engaged in governance for food system change, as well as nutrition and sustainable healthy diets, with additional, albeit weaker, connections to urban food systems transformation, alternative proteins, food waste, and resource-efficient food systems. This reflects the community's focus on the nexus of healthy eating, sustainable production, and more inclusive decision-making. However, the network shows limited engagement with topics such as food from the ocean, the microbiome, food safety, and food systems in Africa. As a result, FoSSNet is not yet well positioned to inform policy on key EU food sources, such as oceans, or on emerging global priorities, including geopolitical instability and the growing role of African countries in the international food system.

Regarding inclusion of non-academic stakeholders in the community, the SNA results should be interpreted with caution. The SNA data did not allow for the categorisation of respondents' contacts by their profession. It was difficult to assess the extent to which these groups are integrated into the network. The strong focus of collaboration on research activities and the limited participation in the survey of these stakeholders itself suggest that these groups may be underrepresented.

The network's focus on governance, nutrition, and sustainable diets demonstrates strong alignment with policy priorities, yet areas such as biodiversity, ecosystems, water resilience, food from the ocean, and African food systems remain underrepresented. Limited inclusion of non-academic stakeholders further indicates that connections between science, policy, and society are not yet fully embedded, which may constrain the broader uptake of knowledge. Strengthening cross-scale integration and diversifying participation are therefore critical to ensure that FoSSNet can effectively inform policy, support sustainable food system transformation, and make the interface between science, policy, and society more resilient and inclusive.

From these structural characteristics, the SNA identified six key gaps-challenges: (1) lack of bridges between and within communities; (2) vulnerability of a hub-driven network; (3) lack of collaboration beyond research; (4) limited engagement beyond academia; (5) limited role of early-career researchers; and (6) uneven geographical coverage. Participants at the feedback workshops emphasised the connections between the gaps and their underlying causes. These connections are seen between Gap 1 and Gap 6, as the lack of resources and structural funding that support for example inter- and transdisciplinary work has an extended effect on the involvement of the Central and Eastern European FSS community.

Gap 6 and Gap 2 are also connected as the hubs in the network tend to be the well known institutions and individuals with a good reputation. These institutes and

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individuals therefore tend to receive funding as it is perceived by funding agencies less risky than to give funding to lesser known Central or Eastern European institutes and individuals.

Gap 2 is furthermore connected to Gap 5, as ECRs also suffer from the 'genius myth', which creates a lack of diversity in terms of seniority and often gender. It implies that a researcher first needs to have a good scientific reputation before they are granted access to various FSS communities and networks. Having a few large hubs in a network furthermore often limits the access for new entrants and new innovative perspectives, which are brought by ECRs.

Gap 2 is also connected to Gap 3 as the collaboration beyond research with private companies is often reserved for larger institutes that have the ability to negotiate on better terms with private companies, which is similar to gap 2 where the hubs, i.e. often larger institutes also tend to be preferred by funding agencies compared to smaller institutes and organisations.

Gap 3 and Gap 1 have in common that the lack of transdisciplinarity (i.e. collaboration beyond research) stems from a lack of incentives that support and value this kind of research and also the lack of a common language which is not jargon filled.

Gap 3 and Gap 4 have been interpreted by workshop participants in the same way: lack of collaboration beyond research and limited engagement beyond academics are seemingly the same. Gap 3 actually refers to the activities that can be part collaboration within the research and academic community, i.e. linked to the functions described in section 2.2. It means that FSS researchers, for example, are less inclined to collaborate on policy engagement or developing new curricula for education and capacity building than research. Gap 4 focuses more on the type of actors: academics, policy makers, private sector and civil society.

Beyond this 'misinterpretation' of Gap 3 by many workshop participants, the connection with Gap 4 is about the ability to engage with the private sector in terms of the timelines, market needs and real-world conditions. Other challenges that hamper engagement beyond academic and research activities relate to differences between academia and private sector in research agendas, language, and definitions. Finally, the ability to negotiate the terms of collaboration between academia and the private sector, also seen as a link to Gap 2, on intellectual property rights for example, are a key factor.

Finally, Gap 4 and Gap 1 are connected by the lack of transdisciplinary, which according to Gap 4 results is also related to a lack of trust between various actors, of which data privacy issues are a part.

In sum, the feedback workshop results gave insights into the underlying causes and the systemic relations between the gaps. It shows that addressing one gap or issue might be a lever to address multiple gaps and issues. In particular the following points deserve attention: First, interdisciplinarity is currently faced by barriers such as a silo mentality, language or jargon issues, and different non-collaborative institutional incentives. This is exacerbated by a difficulty in publishing inter- or trans-disciplinary research results.

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Second, transdisciplinarity, which involves other actors in the FS through participatory processes was deemed important by the feedback workshop participants. Workshop participants, however, indicated that they often lack the tools to engage in a meaningful way with other stakeholders. And here again they face challenges related to language and a difference in timelines between science and the private sector. Hence, working in a transdisciplinary fashion is currently not well supported in the various communities across the FSS landscape. Third, in terms of inclusivity, there are elements in the current network constellation that create a form of gate keeping, in particular for ECRs and Central and Eastern European institutes. The elements include the reliance on a small number of hubs and the focus on joint research only, rather than the other functions of a FSS network.

5.2 Limitations of the study

Several limitations should be considered when interpreting the findings. The sampling and the survey method introduced strong biases in the study. For the continuation of the study, alterations to the research design are required.

First, although there are no universal standards for acceptable minimum response rates or sample sizes (Guerrero et al., 2020), SNA performs best when response rates are high (sometimes as high as 80–100%) (Agneessens & Labianca, 2022). Most SNA surveys do not reach this level. This is a common limitation of web-based surveys. As a result, the structural gaps and cohesion patterns identified through network metrics should be interpreted with caution. This SNA should not be extrapolated to represent the full population of food systems scientists in the broader FoSSNet community and Europe. Missing actors and ties may alter centrality measures, density estimates, and the identification of key brokers. That said, the preliminary results were presented and discussed during national feedback workshops, where partners reflected on and broadly validated the observed patterns. This process provided contextualisation and increased confidence that the main structural features identified by the analysis resonate with participants' experience, even if the constructed network cannot be considered accurate.

Second, the scope of the network was constrained by the survey design. Respondents were asked to nominate up to five to ten close collaborators. For individuals with more extensive collaboration portfolios, this limit may have resulted in the omission of important ties, leading to a partial representation of their professional networks. Consequently, the overall network structure may underrepresent the true extent of connectivity within the community. Relatedly, the nomination limit likely introduced a bias towards strong ties. Occasional, emerging, or informal collaborations that may be crucial for innovation and knowledge diffusion may have been excluded. In addition, relationships among the named contacts were only captured if explicitly reported, meaning that some indirect or unobserved ties may be absent from the dataset. Together, these factors may contribute to an underestimation of network cohesion and cross-cluster connectivity, particularly where weaker bridging ties play an important role.

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Furthermore, due to privacy and data protection considerations, individual actors cannot be explicitly identified in the analysis. While network metrics (e.g. centrality measures) allow the detection of structurally important positions, the anonymity of respondents prevents the public attribution of these roles to specific individuals. As a result, the analysis can highlight patterns of influence, brokerage, or cohesion, but it cannot formally designate particular persons as key actors.

Given the relatively low response rate and the limit on the number of collaborators each respondent could name, repeating the same SNA survey at the end of the project is unlikely to provide a reliable picture of how the network is changing over time. Small differences in who responds could appear as a structural change, even if the underlying network has not shifted substantially.

A more practical approach would be to identify a small number of clear and meaningful indicators that reflect the kind of network the consortium aims to build, and to track these as part of a Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning (MEL) framework. For example, this could include tracking the extent of collaboration across countries and scales, the diversity of sectors involved, or the number of new partnerships formed through consortium activities. These indicators would be easier to collect and place less burden on members. Periodic network mapping could still be undertaken as a complementary exercise to reflect on overall structure and dynamics, but not as the main tool for tracking change over time.

The feedback workshop provided additional insights to the identified gaps and gave them more meaning. On the one hand the workshop created an opportunity to invite additional people, who may or may not have been included in the initial SNA results. The workshop also provided an additional opportunity for data collection. On the other hand, every type of workshop has its own biases, as there is always a selection bias regarding the invitees. In part this is due to the available space, budget, or timing. And then there is a self-selection bias as not all invitees are able to attend at the chosen moment. While the latter point was made somewhat easier by the possibility to do a hybrid or fully online workshop, still the number of participants was relatively low in a few countries. Some solved it by paying attention to only one or a few of the SNA identified gaps, allowing for a longer and more in-depth discussion. In addition, some partners struggled to create a more national focus to their workshop and mainly had participants who were part of their own institution.

5.3 Recommendations

It has been argued above that a food systems science network could function and contribute effectively as part of the European science-policy-society interface (SPSI) for food systems. To develop the FoSSNet community into such a functional network, it is necessary to build bridges across sectors, establishing direct links between researchers and policymakers, investors, and practitioners, not only mediated through a few central actors. To ensure knowledge and lessons can diffuse cross-scale, there should be connections between local experimentation (e.g. living labs), national

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initiatives, and EU-level programming. To diffuse food system literacy internally, stronger peer-to-peer exchange among educators, early career researchers, and leadership is needed.

Based on the results of the study and suggestions from participants in the workshops, recommendations are presented for facilitating relations and strengthening the integration within a food systems science network:

1. Enable connections between research communities

Provide a platform for making curiosity-driven connections on specific topics or disciplines. A possible approach is to facilitate (short-term) collaboration at the interface of two (or more) disciplines, who jointly have to answer a specific research question – the principle of a knowledge hub. This enhances (new) linkages between network members, which can support the involvement of early career researchers (ECR). ECRs in one discipline have suggested an interest in a mentoring or connection with advanced researchers in other disciplines. In general, junior-senior partnering allows juniors to show their potential and allow seniors to offload some work. Further, it could enhance the position of members from Central and Eastern European countries if they are incorporated in these schemes.

2. Support non-academic engagement

Provide a dedicated platform to match research needs with practitioner expertise, facilitate collaborations between academia, industry, policy, and civil society. These spaces can ensure that, through stakeholder engagement, the most vulnerable and underrepresented actors in the system are being heard. It thus requires the design of activities that give opportunities for non-academic voices to be integrated in the research agenda. Organising spaces for dialogue, facilitating a constant flow of information and exchanges using a common language will help to make this ambition work. Tailored communication (e.g., specific newsletters, advisory boards) is necessary to connect effectively with policymakers, funding agencies, industry, and civil society.

3. Education

There is a clear interest in ensuring more food systems literacy for academics and non-academics, across age groups, and stages of learning and professional life. This need can be met through the development of training programmes and education curricula that include interdisciplinary approaches and that ensure the skills and knowledge gained are relevant and applicable to societal needs. It also requires training and supporting skilled intermediaries or translators within the food system, which could also support a better understanding of regional differences. Additionally, education can also involve the promotion and strengthening of the role of senior academics in supporting ECRs in building competencies beyond research (i.e. grant writing, participation in coordination activities, facilitate access to relevant networks). The creation and organisation of mentorship opportunities for ECRs would support this ambition.

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4. Mobility

Facilitate connections between institutions for mobility and staff exchanges across countries to enhance knowledge circulation and more balanced network participation. This should also benefit ECRs and increase their awareness of relevant networks and opportunities. For ECRs, the benefits and terms of participation (i.e. what they can gain by being part of a specific network) should be clear. This can partially address the issue related to time constraints and prioritisation, giving them a reason to create more space for participation. Greater mobility can support the creation of local hubs or regional nodes that facilitate connections with broader European networks

5. Governance

For FoSSNet, as a goal-directed organisational network with a distinct identity and legacy, governance is needed to ensure collective action, manage conflict, and use resources effectively. Drawing on network theory and governance scholarship, the organisation of a food systems science network like FoSSNet should deliberately balance brokerage and cohesion (Bodin & Crona, 2009; Burt, 2004; Reagans & Zuckerman, 2001), and adaptive governance (Folke et al., 2005; Provan & Kenis, 2008). This suggests organising the network into strong thematic groups, while ensuring that some members - as brokers - actively connect these groups. Provan & Kenis (2008) argue that network effectiveness depends on matching governance structure to network characteristics including trust among members, number of participants, goal consensus, and the need for coordination capacity. Several recommendations have been proposed to strengthen trust, including fostering a sense of togetherness through a shared work culture and language, and establishing a policy working group to advocate for funding mechanisms that reduce dependence on a central hub. Examples include creating new connections between members through senior-junior partnerships and enhancing collaboration with network members from Central and Eastern Europe. Cocreation models (e.g., learning labs and networks) that include non-research partners with clear frameworks for balancing power, defining mutual benefits, and protecting weaker actors can strengthen trust and coordination.

6. Funding

Create opportunities for collaboration by raising awareness of available funding schemes, calls and networking events. This should include a strategy to secure long-term funding to be able to build a community and trusted relationships that go beyond the short-term project outputs. This also requires advocating for adjustments to EU funding mechanisms to reduce the concentration of funding and coordination roles in Western Europe.

7. Brokering role

Altogether what is required of a FSS network is to develop a clear role as a broker. Through dedicated facilitators and intermediaries, a network can bridge disciplinary and

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sectoral languages, manage power dynamics, and align differing expectations on timelines and outputs, making collaborations more inclusive and effective.

It thus acts as a connector that actively facilitates inter- and transdisciplinary networking through the creation of spaces for dialogue across regions; advocates and promotes policies that enable the building bridges; supports knowledge cocreation and exchange using a common language; facilitates a constant targeted flow of information to a broader audience.

On the road towards achieving this vision, the SNA analysis results can be used in outreach and communication to increase the visibility of food systems science and transition approaches among policymakers, academic institutions, networks, and the media, enhancing the overall impact of FoSSNet's efforts toward food systems transformation. However, it remains to be seen how academics and stakeholders outside of FoSSNet will view the proposition for a food system science network or the need for closer collaboration. Initial feedback from the feedback workshops and other engagement has shown positive sentiments from the stakeholder community, but further consultation with food system actors is required to validate these views.

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Appendix I

FoSSNet SNA survey - Feedback Workshop

Start of Block: Introduction text

Q1 FoSSNet is a 4-year Horizon Europe funded project dedicated to establishing a pan-European network for Food Systems Science (FSS), advancing open and inclusive science and education for food systems transformation. This study uses Social Network Analysis (SNA) to support FoSSNet's goal of building stronger academic networks for Europe's food systems. The study maps relationships between individuals, organizations, and networks within FoSSNet to identify opportunities for stronger collaboration. Through understanding these connections, the SNA aims to support a resilient, sustainable, and inclusive food systems science network.

Consent form text

As a participant in the FoSSNet workshops, you have been invited to answer this questionnaire. The questionnaire will take about 15-20 minutes of your time. Your participation is voluntary. You can skip any questions (select the Skip button) and stop participating (close the questionnaire) without having to provide any reasons. Type of data collected To analyse the social network of FoSSNet, we will collect your personal data, including your name, gender, email, affiliation, field of expertise, FSS projects and FSS networks which you work on/are members of. We will also ask you to share personal information of your contacts with whom you collaborate on food system science, including their names, fields of expertise, affiliations and their work related to food system science. Vice versa, if another respondent mentions you as a contact, they will share such information about you. Use of data Wageningen University & Research (WUR), Oxford University and Lund university researchers (co-lead of the study); Roskilde University (the project coordinator) will have access to your identifying information. Other researchers who will work with the data will not be able to link the research data to you as a participant, thanks to pseudonymization. Your pseudonymized information will be used in the project's reports and scientific publications. In publications, it will not be possible to trace the information back to you, as your names and specific details will not be included in any publications. Protection and storage of data During data collection, your personal data will be recorded and stored on Qualtrics (the survey platform) server. Once data collection completes, the data will be downloaded and stored on WUR's and Roskilde University (the project coordinator)'s Microsoft SharePoint. Please read the full consent form with more information about

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the study before proceeding with the questionnaire by clicking here:
Informed_consent_REC_SNA_FoSSNet_revised_national.docx

Q3 Please read these two statements BELOW carefully before answering to give your consent: By answering "Yes" you agree that you have read through the consent form and understand the purpose of the study and what data you are providing. By answering "Yes" you consent in participating in this research and to the use of your personal data as described.

Yes (1)

No (2)

End of Block: Introduction text

Start of Block: Respondent information

Q4 Q.1 Full Name:

Q5 Q.2 Gender

Male (1)

Female (2)

Non-binary / gender diverse (3)

Prefer not to say (4)

Q6 Q.3 Age

18-35 (1)

36-50 (2)

51-65 (3)

65+ (5)

Prefer not to say (4)

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Q7 Q.4 Primary Institution or organisation (Affiliation):

Q8 Q.5 My main occupation is:

Scientist (1)

Policy maker (2)

Administrator (3)

Private industry representative (4)

Civil society representative (5)

Other namely: (6) _____

Q9 Q.6 Focus of career: Please indicate your level of focus for each area

	Strong focus (1)	Somewhat focused (2)	Weak focus (3)	No focus (4)
Education (1)				
Policy (2)				
Research (3)				
Communication (4)				
Private sector (5)				

Q10 Q.7 At what stage of your career do you consider yourself:

Junior (1)

Medior (2)

Senior (3)

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Q11 Q.8 What is your field/s of expertise:

- Social Sciences (1)
 - Humanities (10)
 - Environmental Sciences (2)
 - Food Sciences (3)
 - Formal Science (11)
 - Life sciences (4)
 - Physical sciences (12)
 - Applied sciences (5)
 - Applied Systems science (6)
 - Education Innovation (7)
 - Business creation (8)
 - Agricultural Sciences (13)
 - Economics (14)
 - Political Sciences (15)
 - Nutrition & Health (16)
 - Science Communication (17)
 - Other namely: (9) _____
-

Q41

The next set of questions are about the work you do on Food System Science. For the FossNet project, we use the following framework for food systems. For our definition of Food Systems aspects, please refer to the definitions below: Drivers: Activities and actors are all influenced by certain "drivers" (processes determining how these activities are performed. Activities: A food system is made up of food system activities (growing, harvesting, processing, packaging, transporting, marketing, consuming, and disposing of food and food-related items) Outcomes: Outcomes refer to the outputs of food systems, which are shaped by the interactions between drivers and activities. Feedbacks: outcomes, in turn, feed back to environmental and socio-economic drivers

Q21 Q.8b Please indicate your level of focus on food system science in your work profile:

- Low (1)
 - Medium (2)
 - High (3)
-

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Q12 Q.9 The focus of your work is on which type of FSS aspects (check all that apply):

- Drivers (1)
- Activities (2)
- Outcomes (3)
- Feedbacks (4)
- Relationships/interactions between 2 aspects above (6)
- Relationships/interactions between 3 aspects above or more (7)
- Other namely (5) _____

Q42 In this section of the survey, we would like to know about your collaborations, starting with projects and networks you are involved in. Following this, we would like to know about your relationships with colleagues within and outside the FoSSNet project, both within and outside your organisation. We are curious about the specifics of what you collaborate on with the colleagues you name.

Q22 Q.9b How well connected do you consider yourself to be within the food system science community?

- Not at all connected (1)
- Slightly connected (2)
- Moderately connected (3)
- Well connected (4)
- Very well connected (5)

Q14 Q.10 Please list up to 5 current FSS projects you are involved in. If not applicable leave blank.

	scale
Project 1 (1)	▼ grassroots/local (1 ... Global (4)
Project 2 (2)	▼ grassroots/local (1 ... Global (4)
Project 3 (3)	▼ grassroots/local (1 ... Global (4)
Project 4 (4)	▼ grassroots/local (1 ... Global (4)
Project 5 (5)	▼ grassroots/local (1 ... Global (4)

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JS

Q22 Q.11 Please list 5 organized networks you are currently a member of that participates in FSS activities and provide a website/source we can use to verify it. If not applicable, leave blank. For a working definition of network we refer to the following: A network consists of stakeholders representing the interests of one or more sectors in science, government, citizens, private business, connected via collaborative research, funding partnerships, or policy advisory roles that facilitate the exchange of knowledge, resources and information.

	Network Name	Scale of network	Verification for Network
	Name (1)		Link (1)
Network 1 (1)	•	▼ Grassroots/local (1 ... Global (4)	•
Network 2 (2)	•	▼ Grassroots/local (1 ... Global (4)	•
Network 3 (3)	•	▼ Grassroots/local (1 ... Global (4)	•
Network 4 (4)	•	▼ Grassroots/local (1 ... Global (4)	•
Network 5 (5)	•	▼ Grassroots/local (1 ... Global (4)	•

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End of Block: Respondent information

Start of Block: Network of individuals and collaborations - named individuals

Q15 Q.12 Please list the top 10 people (within and outside your organisation) you collaborate with on FSS activities and their organisation. If you prefer not to name them for any reason, please use the pseudonym "Person X" in the "Full name" text box, along with their organisation. If not applicable leave blank.

	Full name (1)	Organisation (2)
Person 1	•	•
Person 2	•	•
Person ...	•	•
Person 10 (10)	•	•

Q23 Q.12b How many additional people (beyond the top 10 you listed) do you work with on food system science (FSS) activities?

Fewer than 10 (1)

10 - 30 (2)

More than 30 (3)

End of Block: Network of individuals and collaborations - named individuals

Start of Block: Collaboration information for identified colleagues

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Q25 Q.13 How long have you worked with the named People on FSS activities

	How long have you worked with the named people
<code>#{Q15/ChoiceTextEntryValue/1/1}</code> (1)	▼ up to 2 years (1 ... 10+ years (4)

Q47 Q.14 Which of the following collaborations have you engaged with around FSS with the named people? If it is not named, please use the "other namely" text box to specify and select it. If none are applicable to any people, click the next arrow.

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- Research - Applying for research grants (1) •
- Research - Publishing scientific publications (2) •
- Research - Working in projects together (3) •
- Research - Other namely (4) •
- Policy - Members of science advisory board/steering committee (5) •
- Policy - Co-develop calls for grants (6) •
- Policy - Development/formulation of policies (15) •
- Policy - Other namely (7) •
- Education -Development of (bachelors, Masters, Postgraduate programmes (8) •
- Education - Development of career trainings (9) •
- Education - Other namely (10) •
- Communication - Build partnerships (11) •
- Communication - Co-organised events and gatherings (12) •
- Communication - Collaborate on social media platforms and websites (13) •
- Communication - Other namely (14) •

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Private sector - Organise stakeholder dialogues or workshops (16)

•

Private sector - Publishing scientific publications (17)

•

Private sector - Working in projects together (18)

•

Private sector - Bringing innovations to the market (19)

•

Private sector - Broker partnerships (e.g. co-financing) (20)

•

Private sector - Other namely (21)

•

Q23 This is the end of the survey questions, please be aware pressing the next arrow will finish the survey and prevent you going back to check your answers. Before you leave, if you have any final remarks or comments (optional), please write them in the space below.

End of Block: Collaboration information for identified colleagues

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Appendix II

Feedback Workshop Guideline

Workshop overview

Task description

For T2.2.1 all FoSSNet partners will engage twice with peers within their home institutions and own networks.

- **1) workshop aimed at participatory reflection on the results of the first social network analysis (T2.1);**
- 2) workshop to present and reflect on FoSSNet results on FSS in research (D3.2 & D4.3); and FSS in education (D5.2).
- The workshops will result in improved reflection on the quality of the networks for FSS and action agendas for strengthening the networks through the practices of individual scientists, peer groups and science institutions.

Task time line

- First round of feedback workshop (step 1 of T.2.2.1) runs from M14-M22 (March to November 2025).
- Feedback workshops to be held by each partner institution/country **before 1 November 2025**
- National workshop reports to be sent by **1 November 2025**
- Deliverable D2.1 due February 2025

Purpose of the workshop

- Gain feedback and validate initial EU level SNA results
- Gain insights in national perspectives on FSS Networks
- Collect additional data to make SNA more robust
- Opportunity for networking at national level (e.g. start of your national FSS network ?!)

Workshop Time Schedule

What	Time	Who	How
Introduction of FoSSNet & workshop	20 mins	Main facilitator	PPT
Social Network Analysis (SNA) sharing & validation	60 mins	Main facilitator - presentation (30 mins) Group facilitators - group discussion (30 mins)	PPT & Sheets
BREAK	20 mins		
Reflection on the Gaps	Option 1: 45 mins	Group discussion (with facilitators)	Canvas

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	Option 2: 75 mins		
SNA of the workshop participants (survey)	20 mins	All individually	Survey via QR code
Close	15 mins	Main facilitator	PPT
Total time	3-3,5 hours		

Workshop Preparation

Workshop requirements

Number & type of participants:

- 15-20 people max. that work in food system science (e.g. from a science, education, policy perspective)
- Invite potential participants both from within your institution and external networks
- Make sure it is a diverse group (career stage, gender, discipline, etc.)

To organize:

- Pick a date & venue for the workshop
- Select and invite a range of participants
- Complete the participant information on the excel sheet
- Adjust/translate ppt/consent form if needed
- Check the survey in advance

To consider:

- Expect to have to send 30 invites in order to get 15 people
- Use example invitation
- Send reminders if needed
- The workshop can take up to 4 hours including a 30 minute break.
- Perhaps organize a lunch or drinks before/after the workshop to support networking etc. If so – check this with your selected venue and ask for dietary requirements of your participants.
- There is no budget planned for re-imbursing the workshop participants for their time or travel costs.

Workshop Necessities

Roles & Tasks

Overall facilitator of the session

- present the introduction ppt
- introduce colleagues and participants
- check-in with group discussions
- overall time keeping during group discussions
- facilitate plenary sessions

Group facilitators

- Introduce canvas & assignment

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- Guide the process with additional question to create a discussion or to clarify points made by participants
- Provide plenary feedback

General notetaker

- Captures all discussion points during the plenary parts of the workshop (could be done by a group facilitator)

Group notetakers

- Captures all discussion points during the group discussions (either on the canvas, on sticky notes or a large sheet).
- Ideally a separate person, but often done by the group facilitator
- Sometimes done by a participant (risky – you don't know their skill in capturing the essence of a discussion)

Materials

- Room with separate tables
- Laptop & screen
- Adjusted ppt

- Printed consent forms
- Printed canvas (A1)
- Name tags

- Large sheets of paper
- Pens/markers
- Sticky notes
- Tape

- Catering (depending on time schedule). Don't forget to ask dietary requirements of the participants.

Workshop results

Workshop output

- National workshop report
- National level social network analysis – visual and underlying data
- Partner-specific situational analysis of the food systems science network of the FoSSNet members
- Report will be input for report D2.1 = data contributor, possible co-authorship of deliverable.

Post-workshop requirements

- Please write up **the results for each workshop** – outline will be provided
- **Clean the survey data**
- **Upload consent forms** to the national workshop folder on sharepoint
- Don't forget **to communicate the report/SNA results** with workshop participants
- Timeline:
 - **Send workshop report 1 November 2025** latest.
 - Earlier = better (i.e. quicker national SNA results)

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Workshop Runsheet

Time (approx.)	Activity	Instructions/ details	Who leads	Resources
(60 min)	Room setup	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Set-up presentation Ensure tables have all required resources 	Facilitators	PPT presentation Printed Canvas Printed consent forms Name tags Large sheets of paper Sticky notes Marker pens Tape
(20 min)	Opening			
(20 min)	Introduction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome Introduction: quick round table of names Check if everyone signed the consent form Explain purpose of the workshop and background Questions for clarification by participants? 	Main facilitator + General notetaker	PPT
(60 min)	Social Network Analysis			
(40 min)	Sharing SNA results	Presentation of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Method Results Gaps 	Main facilitator	PPT
(20 min)	Plenary discussion (can be done in small groups if easier)	Ask for feedback and validation of the results. Prompting questions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Should anything be added/removed/changed? What stands out for you from these results (positive or negative) What excites or concerns you most? What opportunities and challenges do you see? (segway into the gaps group work) 	Main facilitator + General notetaker	Large sheets Markers/pens Tape
(20 min)	Coffee break & Move to subgroups			
Option 1: 45 mins	Reflection on the gaps			
Option 2: 75 mins				

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<i>Option 1</i> (30 min)	Group discussion of 1 gap per group	Each group gets to choose a gap and follow the instructions on the canvas. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ideally no overlap of gaps between groups It is ok if not all 6 gaps are addressed in the workshops. 	Group Facilitators + Group notetakers Main facilitator as back-up and overall time keeper	PPT Canvas Markers/pens Sticky notes
<i>Option 1</i> (15 min)	Plenary feedback	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Each group facilitator to share key results for the gap from the canvas Approximately 4 minutes per group (4 groups) 	Main Facilitator + Group Facilitators + General notetaker	Canvas Tape
<u>Option 2</u> (50 min)	Group discussion of 2 gaps per group	Each group gets to choose a gap and follow the instructions on the canvas. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> For the 2nd gap please start a new canvas (for clarity for the reporting later). Please try to get all 6 gaps addressed in total between the 2 rounds of discussion. 	Group Facilitators + Group notetakers Main facilitator as back-up and overall time keeper	
<u>Option 2</u> (25 min)	Plenary feedback	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Each group facilitator to share key results for both gaps from the 2 canvasses Approximately 6 minutes per group (4 groups) 	Main Facilitator + Group Facilitators + General notetaker	
(20 min)	SNA of the workshop participants			
(20 min)	Survey	Explain why we ask participants to complete the survey <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Share QR code 	Main facilitator	PTT with QR Code Survey
(15 min)	Close			
(15 min)	Closing and next steps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Thank everyone for their participation. Quick round of feedback on the workshop Next steps: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> National report National SNA results Possible additional national workshop When will you be in touch again? Process FoSSNet/Taks 2.2 Anything else? 	Main facilitator	PPT

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Canvas to print and use during the workshop:

Addressing FSS network gaps	
Identified gap(s)	Understanding the gap What causes this gap? Why is this gap important to address? Who benefits or cares most about closing this gap?
	Closing the gap How can a (mature) network prevent this gap from happening?

 Food Systems Science Network

Appendix III

Scoring		projects + networks																	Overall heatmap					
		FOODPart h5	FoSSNet	CLEVERFOOD	FEAST	CULTIVATE	FOSTER	JRC-EC	COTRANSITION	FutureFoodS	FOOD2030 Network	Food Action and Research Observatory (FARO)	START	AFN Network +	FoSSNet	TUKFS	ForeSight 4Food	FutureFoodS		IFSTAL	STRN	Transitie coalitie v oedsel	University of Copenhagen Green Solutions Centre	
Core FS activities	Producing	1	1	1	2	3	1	3	2	3	3	3	1	2	3	1	2	2	3	1	2	3	3	34
	Processing & manufacturing	2	1	1	2	2	1	3	2	3	3	3	1	1	2	1	2	2	3	1	2	2	2	32
	Waste & surplus food managing	2	1	1	1	3	1	2	1	3	3	3	1	2	3	1	2	2	3	1	2	2	3	32
	Retailing & food service provisioning	2	1	1	2	3	1	3	2	3	2	3	1	1	2	1	2	2	3	1	2	3	2	32
	consuming	2	1	1	2	3	1	3	2	3	3	3	1	3	3	3	3	2	3	1	2	3	3	39
	storing	2	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	3	2	2	1	3	2	1	1	1	3	1	1	1	1	27
	trading	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	3	2	2	1	1	3	1	1	2	3	1	2	2	2	26
	transporting	1	1	1	1	2	1	3	1	3	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	1	3	1	2	1	2	27
	input prices	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	20
	science & technology	3	3	3	3	3	1	1	1	3	2	3	1	3	3	3	3	2	3	3	3	2	3	41
food system conditions	market & trade	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	2	2	3	1	3	1	1	1	2	2	1	2	3	2	26
	consumption patterns	2	2	2	3	2	1	1	2	3	3	3	3	1	3	1	3	2	3	1	2	3	3	37
	policy & governance	3	3	3	3	3	3	1	2	3	3	2	3	2	2	3	2	3	3	1	3	3	3	44
	trust & security	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	3	1	3	2	1	1	3	1	1	2	2	1	25
	investments	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	3	1	3	2	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	24
	labour skills & availability	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	2	3	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	23
	food price	1	2	1	2	1	1	3	1	3	1	1	1	1	2	3	1	1	3	1	1	2	1	26
	animal welfare	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	1	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	21
	antimicrobial resistance	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	1	3	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	23
	education	3	3	1	2	2	1	1	2	2	3	3	3	2	3	3	3	3	2	3	2	2	1	40
social & economic conditions	demographics & epidemics	1	1	1	3	1	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	23
	economic development	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	2	2	3	1	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	1	1	27
	knowledge systems	3	3	3	2	2	3	1	1	2	3	2	1	1	3	3	3	3	2	3	3	2	2	39
	geopolitical process & context	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	1	1	3	1	1	2	1	1	21
	ethics & social values	1	1	1	3	1	1	1	2	2	3	3	3	2	3	1	2	3	2	1	3	3	2	33
	media	1	1	3	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	24
	cultural heritage	3	1	2	3	2	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	3	1	3	2	1	1	2	2	1	30	
	governance systems & power dynamics	1	3	3	2	2	3	1	3	2	3	2	3	2	3	3	2	3	2	1	3	3	3	41
	food & nutrition security status	1	1	1	3	1	1	3	1	3	3	1	1	3	3	1	3	3	3	1	2	2	3	33
	equity & fairness status	2	1	3	3	1	3	1	1	3	2	1	3	2	3	1	2	3	3	1	3	3	2	35
power relations	2	2	3	3	1	1	1	2	1	3	1	3	2	2	2	1	3	1	1	3	3	3	33	
livelihoods & economic status	3	1	1	3	1	1	1	1	3	2	2	3	3	3	1	1	2	3	1	2	1	1	32	
cultural heritage & community building status	2	1	1	3	1	2	2	1	3	2	1	1	1	3	1	3	2	3	1	2	2	1	30	

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Food system elements

environmental conditions	atmosphere	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	2	22		
	biosphere	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	2	22		
	geosphere	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	3	21		
	hydrosphere	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	2	22		
	environmental status	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	1	2	1	1	1	3	1	3	2	1	1	3	1	3	25		
	Horizon Europe Strategic Plan 2025-2027 research and innovation gaps	complex interactions within food systems	3	3	3	3	2	2	1	3	3	1	1	1	1	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	2	3	39
		planetary boundaries and resource use	2	1	1	2	1	1	3	1	2	3	2	3	1	3	1	3	3	2	1	3	2	3	3	33
		climate change impact and mitigation	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	3	3	3	3	1	3	3	1	1	3	2	3	3	31
		biodiversity and ecosystems	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	1	3	2	1	1	3	1	2	3	1	1	2	2	3	3	27
		technological and social innovation	3	2	3	3	3	3	3	2	2	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	2	2	3	3	2	3	3	47
		rural-urban synergies	1	2	2	1	3	2	1	3	1	3	2	1	1	3	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	32
		food systems governance and policy	3	2	3	2	2	3	3	2	2	3	2	3	1	3	3	3	3	2	1	2	3	2	3	43
		nutritional security and safety	2	2	1	3	1	1	1	1	2	3	3	3	2	3	1	3	2	2	1	1	2	3	3	34
		data and digitalisation	1	1	1	1	2	1	3	1	3	3	3	1	3	3	1	2	2	3	1	3	1	3	3	32
		international cooperation	2	3	3	3	2	2	1	1	3	3	2	1	3	2	3	1	3	3	3	3	2	2	3	30
	water resilience	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	2	1	3	3	1	1	3	1	1	2	1	3	3	28	
	Food2030 pathways for action	governance for food systems change	3	3	3	2	2	3	1	3	3	3	2	3	1	3	3	2	3	3	1	3	3	3	3	43
		urban food systems transformation	2	3	3	2	3	2	1	3	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	3	3	35
		food from the ocean and freshwater resources	3	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	1	1	3	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	24	
		alternative proteins for dietary shift	1	2	3	3	1	1	1	3	3	1	3	3	1	2	2	3	1	3	1	2	2	3	3	34
food waste and resource-efficient food systems		1	1	3	1	3	1	3	1	3	1	3	3	1	3	3	3	2	3	1	1	2	3	3	36	
the microbiome world		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	21	
nutrition and sustainable healthy diets		3	3	3	3	3	1	3	3	3	3	3	3	1	3	3	3	2	3	1	1	3	3	3	46	
food safety systems of the future		3	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	3	3	1	2	2	3	2	1	1	1	3	1	3	31	
food systems africa		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	2	2	1	2	19	
data & digital transformation		1	1	3	1	1	1	3	1	3	3	3	1	3	3	2	2	2	3	1	3	1	3	3	34	
zero pollution food systems	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	3	3	1	3	3	3	2	1	1	2	2	3	3	31		